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EDITOR

Dr. Johnson Thomaskutty

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The Editor

masihisevak@gmail.com

Inviting articles, sermons, reflections regarding various aspects of Christian Ministry for the forthcoming issue. Contributions can be addressed to the Editor, masihisevak@gmail.com

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— Editorial

The current issue of the MASIHI SEVAK contains fifteen biblical and theological reflections mostly emerged out of the Indian contextual realities. Majority of the reflections foreground how the authors engaged with the Bible and theological themes from their life situations with groaning hearts. The readers of the reflections can understand the contemporaneous nature and the contextual significance of the Biblical message. I am thankful to the contributors for their timely engagement with the Bible and their hermeneutical groaning for a liberative and transformative endeavours.

Bible engagement is widely practiced in the socio-religious and politico-cultural context of India. As a multi-religious and pluralistic context, people of the nation have varied responses toward the Bible and its message, especially based on their backgrounds.¹ The North-Eastern part of the country was fostering a Biblically-centered cultural dynamics as majority of the people were connected to the ecclesiastical bodies. The relationship between the church and the state in Mizoram and in Nagaland facilitates a Bible-centered culture that influences the people and the society at large. The ethics and ethos of the people

1 Carver T. Yu, "The Bible and Culture in the Shaping of Asian Theology," *Christianity and Cultures: Shaping Christian Thinking in Context*, Regnum Studies in Mission, eds. David Emmanuel Singh and Bernard C. Farr (Carlisle: Regnum Books International, 2008), 51-62.

were often derived from the Bible as the communities accepted it as the measuring rod both in the church and the society.² But under the new political scenario, the influence of the Bible-belt in the North-Eastern states slowly waning as the Hindu nationalistic movement establishes its grips in that region. The Bible culture that is promulgated in several regions of the country, like in Karnataka, Uttar Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Odisha, and other parts, face opposition from the majoritarian nationalistic movements.³ Many missionaries are persecuted due to their faith and practices based on the Bible. In this critical juncture, the Biblical message of groaning remains as a hermeneutical key and as a counter defensive mechanism.

In India, the groaning hearts of the Bible readers persuade them to get involved in the Dalit, Tribal, and Adivasi liberation, emancipation of the women, and transformation of all the 'other' ostracized in the society.⁴ The Dalit Christians in India read the Bible for liberative power and they appropriate their struggles in alignment with the pain and pathos of the people of God inscribed in the scripture.⁵ Though the Dalit Christians are 'ordinary people,' they keep the Bible close to their life situations and apply its message into their day-to-day realities and struggles.⁶ The Dalit Christians consider Bible as their life and daily bread and the very foundation of their existence in the world even when they are in dehumanized situations. They often

2 Zhodi Angami, *Tribals, Empire and God: A Tribal Reading of the Birth of Jesus in Matthew's Gospel* (London: Bloomsbury T&T Clark, 2017), 23-76.

3 Sarbeswar Sahoo, *Pentecostalism and Politics of Conversion in India* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2018), 120-157.

4 Jeeva Kumar Ravela and David J. Chalcraft, "Encountering the Bible: Listening to the Voices of Madiga Christians," *A Biblical Masala: Encountering Diversity in Indian Biblical Studies*, eds. David J. Chalcraft and Zhodi Angami (New Delhi: Christian World Imprints, 2021), 196.

5 Ravela and Chalcraft, "Encountering the Bible," 196.

6 A. P. Nirmal, "Doing Theology from a Dalit Perspective," *A Reader in Dalit Theology*, ed. A. P. Nirmal (Madras: Gurukul Lutheran Theological College and Research Institute, n.d.), 142.

suffer vulnerability in the society due to their status as ‘Dalits,’ and especially as ‘Christian Dalits.’ But the message of the Bible gives them the power of resilience and they sigh deep within themselves irrespective of the growing atrocities around them.⁷ The groanings of the Dalit Christians in India are powerful means to orchestrate a hermeneutic that can facilitate liberative mission.

Just as C. S. Song treated the Bible as a story book and not as a text book,⁸ the tribal communities of the northeastern Indian states treat the Bible as a story book.⁹ Yangkahao Vashum says, “The Bible is a story book. It is filled with the stories of people of faith. They are stories about how God has been faithful to them, how God has been leading and guiding them. They are stories of relations, liberation and life in abundance.”¹⁰ The Bible is placed close to the liberative visions of the tribal communities. The recent conflicts between the Meitei and Kuki communities in Manipur proved that it is an issue between the majoritarian ideology and the minoritarian Christian community. The tribal Christians of the province suffered massive attacks, violences, and vandalisms inflicted upon them by the powerful nationalistic regime. Under the central and state governances, the Meitei community found it easier to inflict attacks on the Kuki community. The Creator God of the Bible can be an all-inclusive reality who can encompass the tribal groanings.¹¹ The majoritarian politics and its nationalistic agenda silence the voices of all the ‘other’ sections of people in

7 Ravela and Chalcraft, “Encountering the Bible,” 215-217.

8 C. S. Song, “In the Beginning were Stories, not Texts,” *Madang International Journal of Contextual Theology in East Asia*, Vol. 14 (15 December 2010), 7-16.

9 Yangkahao Vashum, “Introduction,” *Tribal Theology and the Bible: A Search for Contextual Relevance*, Tribal Study Series 19, ed. Yangkahao Vashum (Jorhat: Tribal Study Center, Eastern Theological College, 2011), 1-9.

10 Vashum, “Introduction,” *Tribal Theology and the Bible*, 2. Also see Hrayr Jebejian, *Bible Engagement: The Discovery of Faith, Hope and Self* (Lebanon: Bible Society in the Gulf, 2019), 115-116.

11 See <https://ntsolarship.wordpress.com/2012/02/27/reading-jesus-paradigmatically-into-the-northeastern-indian-tribal-context/>, accessed on 8 May 2023.

the Indian context. The Christian communities are always at the suffering end. A hermeneutic of groaning can rhetorize the minority sighs for liberative praxes.

The texts such as Genesis 46:28-47:10; 47:13-22; Ruth 1:8-18; Proverbs 3:1-12; Matthew 2:1-18; 5:7; 5:17-20; 25:14-30; Mark 10:13-16; 10:46-52; 14:22-25; Luke 2:25-38; John 15:12-17; 19:25-30; 1 Timothy 5:1-10; and many others are expounded in the following reflections out of the groaning hearts of the authors. Such a hermeneutical and homiletical initiative is the requirement of the current time. Once again, I am thankful to all the contributors for their Bible engagement and resourceful support to the MASIHI SEVAK.

Johnson Thomaskutty,
Editor

1

REFLECTIONS ON THE FIFTH BEATITUDE: “BLESSED ARE THE MERCIFUL, FOR THEY SHALL OBTAIN MERCY” (MATTHEW 5:7)

Joy Philip Kakkanattu, CMI*

“You have come here from kindness and compassion, and, if pity for the sinful be deemed a pious deed, and compassion on those who have gone astray a meritorious act, then shall Heaven reward you for me” – Khalil Gibran.¹

Beatitudes—a Christian programme for discipleship

The beatitudes present a set of values meant as directions for Christian discipleship. Many of them are paradoxical, as “the standards of the world are turned upside down as soon as things are seen in the right perspectives, which is to say, in terms of God’s values, so different from those of the world.”² They provide a roadmap for the Church and set a model for her lifestyle and value system. The fifth beatitude and the theme of mercy have received much attention in recent theological and ecclesial thinking. The theme of mercy is projected to the centre of Christian living and Christian theology in a few noteworthy books.

* Fr. Prof. Joy Philip Kakkanattu is Professor of Old Testament and President of Dharmaram Vidya Kshetram, Bengaluru, India.

1. *The Greatest Works of Khalil Gibran*, “Martha” in Book Seven (Mumbai: Jaico Publishing House, 2005), 17.
2. Joseph Ratzinger, *Jesus of Nazareth: From the Baptism in the Jordan to the Transfiguration*, tran. Adrian J. Walker (New York: Doubleday, 2007), 71.

Cardinal Walter Kasper's statement that mercy is God's gift and a Christian's mission, summarizes the fifth beatitude explicitly. He says: We must practice mercy. We should live and give to witness mercy in word and deed. Thus, a ray of mercy can make a dark and cold world brighter, warmer and a better place to live. Mercy reflects God's holiness in this world and the quintessence of the message of Jesus Christ, which was given to us as a gift and which we are to further bestow on others.³

This beatitude is unique in that it summarizes the character of God in the Bible, in general, and in the New Testament in particular. As Bernard Häring notes: ". . . The revelation of God through the prophets and his final and perfect revelation in Jesus Christ is that of God, who, because of his holiness and absolute perfection, is merciful without end."⁴ In this beatitude, the human attitude "be merciful" (*protasis*) and the divine action "they will have mercy," which is the reason for the blessing (*apodosis*), are expressed in words having the same root *eleein*, "to show mercy." Since the *protasis* "be merciful," and *apodosis*, "will have mercy," are in exact correspondence, as Luz observes, they come close to the idea of a deed that determines fate and "the parenthetical motif of the correspondence of divine and human behaviour."⁵

Mercy comes to those who are merciful. Another uniqueness of this beatitude is that God's dealing with humanity, narrated in the Bible, provides a model for the merciful attitude. In the Sermon on the Plain, Luke articulates mercy as the "deeper Christian principle," as "Be merciful (*oiktirmonēs*), just as your Father is merciful" (Luke 6:36).

3 Cardinal Walter Kasper, *Mercy: The Essence of the Gospel and the Key to Christian Life*, tran. William Madges (New York: Paulist Press, 2013), 218.

4 Bernard Häring, *The Beatitudes: Their personal and social implications* (Slough: St. Paul's Publications, 1976), 49.

5 Ulrich Luz, *Mathew 1-17: A Commentary* (Edinburgh: T&T Clark, 1990), 238.

Analysis of the text

Blessed (makarioi)

Makarioi (blessed) in the secular Greek language is used mainly for gods, who are called blessed (*hoi makares*). It connotes the supreme joy of their life devoid of any anxieties (see 1 Tim 1:11; 6:15, used for God). In the NT, the word indicates the happiness available to humans from their participation in the salvation of the Kingdom of God.⁶ A Beatitude is a solid personal emotional reaction founded on the realization of a promise by God.

The Adjective, 'merciful' (elemon)

The adjective occurs only twice in the NT: Matthew 5:7; Heb 2:17 (the merciful high priest) and in the LXX 30 times. There is another Greek word *oiktirmōn* translated often as "merciful" (see Luke 6:36). These two terms in Greek belong to the same semantic field of mercy. Some authors distinguish between them by saying that *oiktirmōn* refers to the human feeling of mercy and *eleēmōn* refers to the attitude and action of mercy.⁷ In order to understand the nuances of this beatitude, one may have to consider both the terms together as they often occur as a pair (cf. Psa 51:1).

Jesus, the merciful high priest who sympathises with us (Heb 2:17; 4:15)

In Heb 2:17-19, Jesus Christ, the high priest, is presented with two qualities: mercy/compassion and faithfulness. The first refers to his rapport with humans, and the second refers to his rapport with God. What is meant by the merciful attitude of Jesus, the High Priest, is further specified in v.18 and later

6 Klement Stock, *Discorso della montagna Matthew 5-7: le beatitudini* (Roma: Editrice pontificio istituto biblico, 1997), 23.

7 Cf. Geroge Stecker, *The Sermon on the Mount: An Exegetical Commentary*, tran. O. C. Dean (London: T&T Clark, 1988), 39.

in 4:15-5:10. The mercy of Jesus is based on his own experience during the test of suffering and death, and hence he helps those who are tested. Jesus's merciful nature is seen in his readiness to help those who are in need. Since he shared human weaknesses and temptation, Jesus the high priest, sympathizes (*sympathein*)⁸ with us (4:15). Thus, the crucial elements of "being merciful" are compassion and understanding (sympathetic comprehension) of others' infirmity and accompanying efficacious help to lessen the infirmity.

The Noun, "Mercy" (eleos)

The Greek word for mercy, *eleos* corresponds to the Hebrew word *hesed*, which is usually rendered as steadfast or compassionate love. In Latin, it is rendered *miser cordia*. The Greek rendering of *hesed* implies a shift of meaning because in Hebrew, the word *rahamim* expresses the idea of mercy while *hesed* indicates the steadfast love of God.⁹ However, the explication of *hesed* as God's merciful dealing with sinful humanity is seen in many OT texts. In some of the texts (Isa 63:7; Jer 16:5; Hos 2:21; Zech 7:9; Psa 25:6; Lam 3:22; Dan 1:9) *hesed* and *rahamim* are used as synonyms.¹⁰

The noun *eleos* occurs 27 times in the NT.¹¹ It is used 14 times only for God.¹² We analyse only the 7 passages (Matthew 9:13; 12:7; 18:33; 23:23; Luke 10:37; Jam 2:13; 3:17) where the term is used for human mercy. Mathew speaks only of mercy which is

8 "The meaning here, as in 2:16-18 and 5:2, is, more probably, that Christ's earthly life gives him inner understanding of human experience, and thus makes him ready and able to give active help." Ellingworth, *The Epistle to Hebrews*, 268.

9 The Old Testament uses various terminologies to describe God's mercy—the most important ones are *hesed*, *rahamim*, *hanan*, *huz* (pity, but in the affective sense), *emet* (solidarity).

10 See Spieckermann, *Gottes Liebe zu Isarel*, 23.

11 Matthew, 3; Luke, 6; Paul, 10; Jam, 3 the rest 5.

12 In some passages, the mercy of God is presented as the motive of works of salvation, especially in relation to pagans (Rom 11:30-32; Eph 2:4; Tit 3:5; 1 Pet 1:3). It appears 4 times at the beginning of a letter (1 Tim 1:2; 2 Tim 1:2; 2 John 1:3; Jude 1:2); mercy is referred to Jesus and the Father (1 Pet 1:3) and two occurrences refer only to Jesus (Heb 4:26; Jude 1:21).

requested of man (9:13; 12:7; 23:23). All these passages are in the context of controversy between Jesus and the Pharisees. Jesus justifies his conduct by referring to God's mercy and criticizes its deficiency in the Pharisees.

The Pharisees scandalized Jesus for eating with publicans and sinners (Matthew 9:10-13). Jesus, quoting from Hos 6:6 answered them, "Go and learn what it means: 'I wish mercy and not sacrifices'" (Matthew 9:13). Jesus used the same quote to refute the complaint of the Pharisees that his disciples were violating the Sabbath (Matthew 12:7). In verse 23:23, Jesus criticizes the Pharisaic insistence on the practice of law, without paying serious attention to the values inherent in them, when he says, "Woe to you, Scribes and Pharisees, hypocrites! for you tithe mint and dill and cummin, and have neglected the weightier matters of the law, justice and mercy and faith; these you ought to have done, without neglecting the others." The triad, justice, mercy and faith are the underlying covenantal attitudes used to interpret all law. What matters most in moral life, in Jesus's eyes, is justice, mercy, and faithfulness. Whoever wishes to show mercy to a person cannot do otherwise than by respecting his/her right and treating him/her justly, i.e., not condemning him unjustly.¹³ By criticizing the uncaring attitude of the leaders, Jesus here invites "the leaders to manifest a deeper form of authority, namely the quality of mercy, which would unbind the yoke by serving the needs of the people (20:25-27)."¹⁴

These controversies manifest what Jesus meant by mercy/compassion. The publicans and the sinners were marginalized and loathed; the disciples were hungry. So both the groups were in a situation of weakness and infirmity. Instead of rejecting and

13 Eberhard Schockenhoff, *Die Bergpredigt* (Freiburg: Herder, 2014), 162.

14 Michael H. Crosby, *Spirituality of the Beatitudes* (Maryknoll: Orbis Books, 1981), 143.

condemning them, Jesus helped them to better their situation. Jesus is hence the best example of the attitude of mercy.¹⁵

The four other occurrences (Matthew 18:33; Luke 10:37; Jam 2:13; 3:17) make us understand the significance of human compassion. The aspects of mercy that are evidenced here are the need of the neighbour, compassion, and efficacious help.¹⁶ In short, mercifulness is a gracious disposition towards our fellow beings and community members. “It is that kindness and benevolence that feels the miseries of others. It is a spirit that regards with compassion, the sufferings of the afflicted. It is that grace that causes one to deal leniently with an offender and to scorn the taking of revenge . . . The mercifulness of this fifth beatitude is that spontaneous outflow of a heart that is captivated by, and in love with, the mercy of God.”¹⁷ According to James Keenan, mercy is “the willingness to enter into the chaos of another.”¹⁸ The whole salvation history is God’s mercy for humanity. So this beatitude implies, “God, who is mercy, first shows mercy to us and expects mercy from us towards one another.”¹⁹

Parable of the unforgiving servant (Matthew 18:21-34)

The question in 18:33 highlights the reciprocity of divine and human mercy: “Should you not have had mercy on your fellow servant, as I had mercy on you?” This verse and its context is a precious comment on the fifth beatitude. The mercy of the master consists in his response to the plea of the servant, which moved his heart (*splagchnizomai*, Matthew 18:27). The same verb is used

15 Stock, *Discorso*, 89.

16 Stock, *Discorso*, 89.

17 A. W. Pink, *The Beatitudes and the Lord’s Prayer* (Bangalore: Omega Book World, 2022), 38-39.

18 James F. Keenan, *Moral Wisdom: Lessons and Texts from the Catholic Tradition* (Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield, 2004), 72.

19 Yiu Sing Lucas Chan, *The Ten Commandments and the Beatitudes: Biblical Studies and Ethics for Real Life* (Bengaluru: Dharmaram Publications, 2015), 196.

for Jesus, who, moved with pity, accepted the prayer of the two blind men in Matthew 20:34 and he decides to condone the entire debt and let him go free. The lack of mercy of the servant is evident from the attitude to his debtor in his capacity as creditor. In an identical situation of his own, he failed to replicate the merciful dealing of his master.

In this parable, forgiveness is presented as an essential aspect of compassion. This is stressed in the *Our Father*, “forgive us as we forgive” (Matthew 6:12). In fact, the reciprocity of mercy and forgiveness is stressed in the Gospel of Matthew. The verb is used (Matthew 18:27) to indicate the specific attitude expected of the servant in imitation of the master. That is, the master’s act of mercy in the form of writing off the debt and forgiveness should have served as a model for the servant in his dealings in similar situations. In Jam 3:17, compassion is presented as an essential element of true wisdom. The expression, “full of mercy and good fruits” seems to imply that mercy is to be manifested in good deeds.

The verb, “to have mercy (*eleein*)”

The verbal form of *eleos* is *eleein* and is used 32 times in the NT. Its use in the Gospel of Mathew in reference to Jesus is in the context of healing (Matthew 9:27; 15:22; 17:15; 20:30-31). In all these instances, the sick and their relatives invoke Jesus, “Have mercy on me/us” Another verb coming in the semantic domain of mercy is *spalagchnizomai* usually rendered, “to have compassion.” The use of mercy as a noun in Luke 10:37 is connected to this verb.

Mercy as an attitude of heart (*spalagchnizomai*)

The verb *spalagchnizomai* usually rendered, to have compassion, is used in the gospel of Matthew to express the sentiment and response of Jesus to deprived and infirm life-situations. This

verb is used for the effective movement within a person towards a deprivation, which evokes mercy in him/her.

9:36: When he saw the crowds, he had compassion for them, because they were harassed and helpless, like sheep without a shepherd.

14:14: As he went ashore he saw a great throng; and he had compassion on them, and healed their sick.

15:32: Then Jesus called his disciples to him and said, "I have compassion on the crowd, because they have been with me now three days, and have nothing to eat; and I am unwilling to send them away hungry, lest they faint on the way."

20:34: Moved with compassion (following a request for mercy), Jesus touched their eyes. Immediately they regained their sight and followed him.

In all these instances, Jesus's feeling of compassion leads him to do something to address the need that has been recognized and which has moved the heart in its depth. According to Köster, "By the usage of this verb to refer to Jesus, [He] is theologically characterized here as the Messiah in whom the divine mercy is present."²⁰ In Luke 10:37, the neighbour is defined as the one who shows mercy and extends help to a person in need. In the Parable of the Good Samaritan, mercy (*eleos*) is shown as an attitude of the heart (*spalagchnizomai*).

Parable of the Good Samaritan: a parable on the attitude of mercy

In the Parable of the Good Samaritan, the verb *spalagchnizomai* indicates the inner attitude that propelled the Samaritan's pro-active attitude towards the wounded stranger in need.

²⁰ Köster, "*spalagchnon, spalagchnizomai*," TDNT 7: 554.

As Ratzinger observes, the rendering, “he had compassion,” diminishes the original vitality of the Greek word. The verb denotes the movement of the seat of emotions. Seeing the man, the Samaritan’s heart is wrenched open. “Seeing this man in such a state is a blow that strikes him ‘viscerally,’ touching his soul . . . Struck in his soul by the lighting flash of mercy, he himself now becomes a neighbour, heedless of any question of danger.”²¹

In the parable of the Good Samaritan, Jesus broadens the horizon of the understanding of a neighbour. For the OT, the neighbour is a fellow member of one’s people. The covenant community would request each member to support and help others in the community.

Jesus modifies the question from, ‘Who is my neighbour?’ to ‘What is to be done to be a neighbour to a needy person?’ He expands the horizon of ‘neighbour’ beyond the borders of ethnic belonging to human vulnerability. Anyone who is in a vulnerable position becomes a neighbour. One becomes a neighbour to a person, “by caring for him/her in his misery.” One becomes a neighbour when one’s heart and bowels recoil when confronted with suffering and misery, which would prompt one to change one’s itinerary and do what is necessary to alleviate the other’s predicament. The whole of the activity of the Samaritan is understood as an expression of the sentiment of mercy.

The survey of the usage of *spalagchnizomai* evidences that mercy is a movement within a person as a pro-active response to miserable and needy situations. Thus, we can say that mercy denotes a person’s just and correct attitude and conduct to one’s brother or sister who requires help due to a situation of necessity and suffering. It is one’s promptness to get out of one’s own comfort zone to render the help one can extend to the needy. It involves having the courage to approach the needy, not to pass

²¹ Ratzinger, *Jesus of Nazareth*, 197.

them by; it means to have concern for the hapless and helpless and have a readiness to share what we have to restore them. To be merciful is to “become like someone in love, someone whose heart is open to being shaken up by another’s need.”²² It is to have concern for human situations of anguish: hunger, thirst, loneliness, sickness, imprisonment and many others. In other words, it is love manifested in solidarity with the suffering and an efficacious response by doing something creatively to ameliorate their condition.²³

In a certain sense, this beatitude clarifies the first beatitude. Poverty in spirit implies the recognition of total dependence on God. The same dependency is contained in the fact that we sinners, for our salvation and life depend on the mercy of God. The fifth beatitude adds the dependence of our neighbour on us. It would not be sufficient to recognize our dependence on God, and then be indifferent or merciless towards our brothers and sisters, who, in their dire need, seek our help. God’s help becomes effective only when we are ready to help our needy brethren. A passive poverty in spirit is not sufficient; it requires an active commitment to people in necessity. In mercy, God comes very close to humans; in mercy we come close to one another.

This beatitude compliments the fourth (Blessed *are* they which do hunger and thirst after righteousness: for they shall be filled). The right attitude towards others is compassion, which includes ‘being the Good Samaritan, the merciful servant’). The zeal for justice is not expressed in an aversion towards the poor and the weak, but in efficacious compassion.

Conclusion

This beatitude is not the theoretical idealism of a nice attitude. It is to be actualized in the realism of the concrete ministry of

²² Ratzinger, *Jesus of Nazareth*, 197.

²³ John Dominic Crossan, “The Presence of God’s Love in the Power of Jesus’ Works,” *Concilium* 10 (1969), 39.

helping those in need, fighting unjust structures and promoting solidarity. It is an efficacious involvement with the needy. It is an invitation to the Church as a community and to every Christian to witness the good news of God's mercy revealed in Christ. It can be expressed in consoling, pardoning, respecting the dignity of others, acts of amnesty, cancellation of debts, care of the elderly and others. It is expressed in acts of justice and charity (Matthew 25:31-46). In the multi-religious and pluralistic context in India, the practice of this beatitude would be a meaningful means of evangelization that would reveal the real uniqueness of the Gospel message and the Christian way of life.

2

AN ALTERNATE PILGRIMAGE OF JUSTICE AND PEACE

Chilkuri Vasantha Rao*

Introduction

Pilgrimage to holy places constitutes a typical phenomenon in most religious traditions. Pilgrimages are not obligatory, but voluntary and meritorious. In and through this general process of pilgrimage the distinctive regional, cultural and other diversities to some extent become less significant. Pilgrimage is a source both for purification of the soul and for the attainment of objectives related to the problems of mundane existence.

There are several examples of pilgrimage sites of the antiquity, such as: “the statues of Easter Island, Stonehenge in England, Uluru in Australia, the Ring of Brodgar in Orkney, the Teotihuacanos in Central America, Angkor Wat in Cambodia and sacred mountains in China.”¹We learn that the Sumerians of antiquity reverently ascended the steps of the Ziggurat to reach the gate of heaven.² Even today the religious phenomenon of pilgrimage continues in almost all the major religions of the world. Pilgrimages are part of the Hindu tradition from ancient

* Prof. Rev. Dr. Chilkuri Vasantha Rao is Professor of Old Testament and Principal of The United Theological College, Bengaluru, India.

1 Ruth Blackwell, “Motivation for Religious Tourism, Pilgrimage, Festivals and Events,” in *Religious Tourism and Pilgrimage Management: An International Perspective*, eds. R. Raj and N. D. Morpeth (CABI; Oxford, 2007), 36, 5-47.

2 The following is dependent on these sources among others: first, Edith Turner, “Pilgrimage,” *Encyclopedia of Religion*, Vol. II (1987), 327-334, and other articles under this title, see 237-354; second, S. M. Bhardwaj, *Hindu Places of Pilgrimage in India* (London: University of California Press, 1973), 1.

times. Buddhists undertake pilgrimages to the Stupas built with some relic inside it. Tanner writes, "In sub-Saharan Africa there are five types of pilgrimages."³ Muslims from diverse parts of the world undertake the Haj to Mecca. The Jews and Christians too observe this religious practice of pilgrimage.

Alain Marchadour and David Neuhaus rightly observe, "The practice of pilgrimage is one of the most universal dimensions of religion"⁴ and thus it is a Pan-human phenomenon prevalent in almost all religions, though the significance and meaning in each may vary.

Pilgrimage in the Jewish tradition

The Bible gives ample evidence of pilgrimages undertaken by the Hebrew people; for instance, Elkanah, Peninnah and Hannah as a family are seen making their yearly pilgrimage to the ancient shrine at Shiloh (1 Samuel 1). Prophet Elijah, in times of utter despair, is seen journeying all the way to Mount Horeb/Sinai to visit the ancient site of God's theophany (1 Kings 10:8-15). In the history of Israel, it was only after the Josiah's reformation ca. 622 BCE that pilgrimage to the Jerusalem Temple become a religious obligation for every adult male Israelite, to be observed three times a year on the occasion of the celebration of the feast of the Passover, Pentecost and Tabernacles (Deut. 16:16). Jesus being a Jew was no exception to this Jewish religious tradition, he participated by going to Jerusalem on pilgrimages as reported by John in his gospel (2:13; 7:10; 12:12). It was after a pilgrimage to Jerusalem that the Ethiopian eunuch was returning, when Philip meets him on the road to Gaza (Acts 8:27). After the destruction of the second temple in 70 CE the Jews, however, have reorganized their spiritual systems and began the practice

3 R. E. S. Tanner, "Pilgrimage in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Study in the Development of Religious Foci," *J. Soc. Sci.*, 7(2) (2003), 127, 127-135.

4 Alain Marchadour and David Neuhaus, *The Land, the Bible, and History* (New York: Fordham University Press, 2007), 92.

of the three elements such as Prayer, Service and Good Works.⁵ In course of time, as it is evident today, Jews made pilgrimages to the ancient sites of historical importance. In the contemporary times, Jewish pilgrimages are made to the tombs of the Matriarchs, Patriarchs, and to the tombs of other sages. The author himself had the opportunity to pay a visit to some of such tombs in the Holy Land as a participant observer.

Pilgrimage in the Christian tradition

As early as after the resurrection of Jesus the very first believers, who lived in Jerusalem, must have preserved the memory of the locations of the significance to the life and ministry of Jesus, especially of his death and resurrection. These places must have come to be venerated by the faithful in the following generations.

In about 150, the apologist Justin Martyr (d. c. 165) declared that Jesus had been born in a cave not far from Bethlehem. The second-century Palestinian historian Hegesippus knew of the stele and tomb of James, brother of the Lord, "close to the Temple." "Even if few in number, these traditions existed and one can see how they were carefully drawn upon at the beginning of the fourth century in order to form a list of theological holy places. Eusebius of Caesarea refers to them frequently in his *Onomasticon*."⁶

Alain Marchadour and David Neuhaus further observe the historical development of the Christian pilgrimage as follows.

In terms of the Land, Byzantine emperor Constantine's edict of 313, which granted religious freedom to Christians, brought about two important transformations. The first was the establishment of official Christian communities in Jerusalem.

⁵ Class notes from the lecture of Prof. Jesper Svartvik (STI, Jerusalem), 4.3.2016.

⁶ Maraval, *Lieux saints et pèlerinages d' Orient*, 34 (quoted in Alain Marchadour and David Neuhaus, *The Land*, 93.

The second was the development of Christian pilgrimages to the holy places.⁷

This has made the Christian pilgrimage to the Holy Land to be in concrete terms. Christians continue to throng to the Holy Land to have a profound spiritual experience of being in the Land where Jesus ministered and to venerate and pray at the sites of special significance in the life of Jesus Christ especially the places where Jesus was crucified, buried, resurrected and the place of his ascension into heaven.

Pilgrimage to the Holy Land is being more popularized by the number of travel agencies across the world. Modern flight connections to the Holy Land, comfortable hotel facilities and good local logistic arrangements are an encouragement to many of the middle-class Christians even from the poorer countries of the world to undertake this pilgrimage to the Holy Land. Some men and women even go the extent of even spending their whole life's investments for this one and the only trip that they could make in their life time. Many elderly, who even have difficulty in free physical mobility venture into this pilgrimage to the Holy Land. This phenomenon continues and is growing year after year bringing Christian pilgrims to the Holy Land. It is noteworthy that the nature of pilgrims and pilgrimages is undergoing a metamorphosis in course of the passage of time.

Pilgrimage mixed with religious tourism

We have been with the understanding that each religious group exclusively visits only the holy sites connected to his or her own religious tradition, but when we observe closely there are other behavioral patterns that could be noted in the pilgrim's lives. In one of my earlier studies of a Christian pilgrimage in India it was observed, "While interviewing in the villages surrounding Luxittipet a number of Hindus said they had participated in

⁷ Marchadour and Neuhaus, *The Land*, 93.

the Christian Jathara.”⁸ This is very interesting that the Hindus attending a Christian pilgrimage. Even the reverse of this process could be observed that Possnet of Medak a Methodist missionary to India had the custom of taking his theological students to the Hindu pilgrimage sites in order to distribute tracts. It is during this time Possnet and his students met so many Christians who were members of their own congregations. It has been my personal experience of going as a wandering sadhu (a religious ascetic) to the Hindu pilgrim centers in the Himalayas; a Christian is visiting Hindu pilgrim sites!⁹ In earlier research I had documented how both Hindus and Muslims have been attending Christian pilgrimages.¹⁰ It is also a common sight in India where some Christians as well as some Hindus visit Muslim pilgrim sites. Today there are number of pilgrims from India coming to the Holy Land and some of them are Hindus who are joining their Christian friends. In the Bible we find an instance of a Syrian commander Naaman making a pilgrimage¹¹ to the river Jordan with a desire to be healed from leprosy (2 Kings 5).

This cross cultural and multi-faith phenomenon is called as Religious Tourism, where a person not necessarily belonging to the faith tradition yet ventures into visiting holy sites of other religious tradition. “Religious tourism, therefore, encompasses all kinds of travel that is motivated by religion and where the destination is a religious site.”¹² This could happen for various reasons and several motives. Even Christians visiting Holy Land venture into visiting the Western Wall in Jerusalem or visit to the

8 Chilkuri Vasantha Rao, *Jathara: A Festival of Christian Witness* (Secunderabad: CSI Diocese of Medak, 1997), 15.

9 My experience is recounted in Chilkuri Vasantha Rao, *Heads and Tales* (Secunderabad: Medak Diocese, 2008), 1-11.

10 See Vasantha Rao, *Jathara*, 100-108.

11 This is termed as pilgrimage by Alain Marchadour and David Neuhaus, *The Land*, 92.

12 Ruth Blackwell, “Motivation for Religious Tourism,” 37.

Rachel's Tomb on the way to Bethlehem and our group we had visited the mosque that is right in front of the Church of Nativity in Bethlehem. In a globalized world, there are many voices that motivate a person to undertake pilgrimage and many a time it would be more a sort of mixed with religious tourism attracted by probably a long travel, visiting sites that are uncommon such as places with scenic beauty, rare rivers, high mountains, unique flora and fauna and the like. Some are even clubbed with commercial interests, since some in India have begun to sell Jordan water to be mixed with the baptismal waters, wine from the Holy Land to be mixed in the communion wine, Olive oil to be applied for healing. Some have even gone to the extent of mixing sand from the Holy land in the ground breaking ceremonies. Some are taking the innocent Christians to believe that if the sand from the Holy Land is mixed with the mud from the graves of the departed relatives that their souls will go to Heaven. An appalling return to the dark period of Middle Ages. As long as Christians lay importance to the one place called Holy Land, many myths begin to surround it, people will be easily misled to lay stress on the erroneous aspects in their life than to be aware of the call of Jesus Christ to live a life lived with the values of the kingdom of God, molding one's life into a life committed to Justice with peace. It is these elements that have to motivate Christian life. Holy Land visit could never substitute for doing justice and working for peace. In this context the question that becomes relevant is, if an alternate pilgrimage possible which could be more meaningful for a true Christian witness.

A call for alternate pilgrimage of justice and peace

In the whole process of making a pilgrimage to the holy land, indulging in religious tourism and not being sensitive to the very socio-political context in which this pilgrimage is happening would be like moving dead stones. There are cries everywhere

for justice and peace in this land. I have watched in the YouTube¹³ Bishop Munib A. Younan of the Evangelical Lutheran Church in Jordan and the Holy Land calling pilgrims to come to the Holy Land and visit the Living Stones, he was calling the pilgrims to have open eyes to see the reality of the Palestinian-Israeli conflict¹⁴ and open ears to hear the cries of the oppressed and thus have a heart to involve oneself and work for justice and peace in one's own way. This is the way of a righteous pilgrimage committed for justice and peace. When we are on such a pilgrimage then we open our eyes and ears and we inform ourselves of the conflict situation.

Amos Oz explains that both the traumatized Israelis and traumatized Palestinians in conflict are the victims of one and the same oppressor, he says, "Europe-which colonized the Arab world, exploited it, humiliated it, trampled upon its culture, controlled it and used it as an imperialistic playground-is the same Europe that discriminated against the Jews, persecuted them, harassed them, and finally, mass-murdered them in an unprecedented crime of genocide."¹⁵ It is very important for us to see the Israeli-Palestinian conflict in its historical background. Amos Oz explains the plight of the Israelis as:

Israeli Jews, really are a bunch of half-hysterical refugees and survivors, haunted by dreadful nightmares, traumatized not only by Europe but also by the way we were treated in Arabic and Islamic countries. Half the population of Israel consists of people who were kicked out of Arabic and Islamic countries. Israel is indeed one large Jewish refugee camp. Though half of us are actually Jewish refugees from Arab

13 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TbSzIscgTLM>.

14 For a historical overview of the conflict read Martin Bunton, *The Palestinian-Israeli Conflict: A Very Short Introduction* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2013).

15 Amos Oz, *How to Cure a Fanatic* (New Jersey: Princeton University Press, 2010), 15.

countries, Arabs do not see us this way; they see us as an extension of colonialism.¹⁶

On the other hand, the cries of the Palestinians explain their deplorable situations they face due to Israelis erecting the separation wall, Israeli settlements, humiliation at the military checkpoints, separation between members of the same family, emigration, restriction of religious liberty, while many still living in camps under difficult circumstances and others serving imprisonment in the name of security, control of natural resources and being deprived of freedom. The call of the Palestinians to the Israelis is heard through the Kairos Palestine document:

In the face of this reality, Israel justifies its actions as self-defense, including occupation, collective punishment and all other forms of reprisals against the Palestinians. In our opinion, this vision is a reversal of reality. Yes, there is Palestinian resistance to the occupation. However, if there were no occupation, there would be no resistance, no fear and no insecurity. This is our understanding of the situation. Therefore, we call on the Israelis to end the occupation. Then they will see a new world in which there is no fear, no threat but rather security, justice and peace.¹⁷

Hearing both the voices in conflict certainly makes one already part of the situation and one is called for a right response. Both invite for appropriate action. Amos Oz says that it is easier to solve the issue if both the victims would for themselves come together and decide for themselves their future. He further states, "You no longer have to choose between being pro-Israel and pro-Palestine. You have to be pro-peace."¹⁸ Raising a ray of hope, the Kairos Palestine document also calls in similar tone

16 Oz, *How to Cure a Fanatic*, 16-17.

17 Kairos Palestine, *A Moment of Truth* (Jerusalem: Patriarchs and Heads of Churches, 2009), 6.

18 Oz, *How to Cure a Fanatic*, 15.

of mutuality: “Our appeal is to reach a common vision, built on equality and sharing, not on superiority, negation of the other or aggression, using the pretext of fear and security. We say that love is possible and mutual trust is possible. Thus, peace is possible and definitive reconciliation also. Thus, justice and security will be attained for all.”¹⁹ Both affirm justice to be the yardstick and peace to be the outcome.

Our pilgrimage becomes a pilgrimage for justice and peace. Just as when the disciples asked Jesus, where he stayed, Jesus said, come and see (John 1:38-39). We are called to come and see where Jesus stayed, called as Holy Land, a place torn with strife and conflict. This pilgrimage continues in our lives until justice is done and peace prevails.

One good example of this alternate pilgrimage is the World Council of Churches’ ‘pilgrimage of Justice and peace.’ In 2016 Lent, the Israel-Palestine conflict was in the focus and there was a call to the world community of faith to pray and strive for justice especially for water justice for the Palestinians, as the need of the hour. At the service on the Ash Wednesday at the Redeemer Lutheran Church the WCC inaugurated the seven weeks of Water Lent Campaign. By way of conclusion I would say that we need to create time and space in our pilgrimages to look into the socio-economic, religio-political realities of the place and incorporate them into our meditations, prayers, sermons, presentations and in our respective countries and congregations, encouraging them for pilgrimages of justice and peace.

¹⁹ Kairos Palestine, *A Moment of Truth*, 16-17.

3

A RESPONSIBLY ROOTED ECONOMY OF LIFE!

A REFLECTION BASED ON GENESIS 47:13-22

Rohan P. Gideon*

Prayer:

Dear God, as storytellers we shape your unfolding story. As passionate people we share your passion for justice. As bearers of your image, we embody your life in the world. Humble us to listen to forgotten stories. Empower us with boldness when we are afraid. Re-source us for the birthing of liberation, Amen.

When Leo Tolstoy, the celebrated novelist from Russia, was asked which story in the Bible influenced him the most, he seemed to have immediately singled-out the story of Joseph because Tolstoy saw parallels of his own life in the story of Joseph. Tolstoy was orphaned at any early age and he and his siblings were eventually forced to move from their childhood home to a distant city. For much of his youth, Tolstoy saw the young Joseph in him, dreaming to get back to where he thought he actually belonged while making a life for himself elsewhere. It is understood that Tolstoy eventually returned to his home, but what haunted him for the rest of his life was the sense of abandonment, betrayal that had driven him out and the desire to belong among his own folks as rootedly as he wished.

As we read the stories of the Bible, which parts of our lives find parallels in the biblical legends have been a hermeneutical

* Prof. Rev. Dr. Rohan P. Gideon is Professor of Theology at The United Theological College, Bengaluru, India.

debate. More importantly, which specific aspects of the lives of the Biblical legends we wish to identify ourselves will decide whether we intend to be prophetic or play safe. Tolstoy took the 'rags to riches' narrative of Joseph.

The Joseph narrative in the Old Testament has problematic aspects about the way Joseph handled his administrative responsibilities which our Christian education, regular sermons in the churches, our bible studies do not wish to engage with. And we as priests, theologians and leaders are selective in choosing the verses from today's passage in interpreting the life of Joseph to fit our own desires and benefits. My reflections largely draw insights and perspectives from vv. 20-22 while engaging with the rest of the read passage:

"So, Joseph bought all the land of Egypt for Pharaoh. All the Egyptians sold their fields, because the famine was severe upon them; and the land became Pharaoh's. As for the people, he made slaves of them from one end of Egypt to the other. Only the land of the priests he did not buy; for the priests had a fixed allowance from Pharaoh, and lived on the allowance that Pharaoh gave them; therefore, they did not sell their land."

The passage calls for an introspection alongside being retrospective especially in the light of our theme *Responsible Freedom*. I call my reflection *A Responsibly Rooted Economy of Life*.

I wish to explain the phrase *Responsibly Rooted Economy of Life* thus: Through the responsibilities that we are given and for the freedom that we enjoy, we need to deliberately develop a deep idea of life, sustenance and solidarity. In this process, I believe it is important to go back to our own roots, to our earlier years, to our past experiences to see:

if we were once victimised or wronged against, and what were some of the most vulnerable situations we have had been in;

how the memories of such victimisation have conditioned our mindset to address the situations of victimization around us; when we are in the positions of power to make decisions or even in a position influence the decisions, what do we become: perpetrators of violence or exhibited a sense of empathy to the victims?

Most importantly, what mindset takes over when we are in the position of power:

Will it be a selective amnesia that we were once victims, and now it is our time enjoy the power and privilege that we were deprived of? or

Will it be a sense of deeply rooted solidarity that we will not let recreate a sense of slavery or vulnerability because we did not like to be slaves and vulnerable ourselves?

Three insights from this passage help us discern the theme *A Responsibly Rooted Economy of Life* more deeply as follows.

Our understanding of economy must be life-centred

Economy here is not just the financial management of a local state or at the national level. Here economy means how we run our own lives, our families, our immediate communities and how we address our existential questions in ways that 'life and life in fulness' becomes the central objective.

The setting of the passage is a double economic crisis that has hit very hard the lives of the people of Egypt. The first level of crisis is caused by famine. But my attention is on the artificial crisis that Joseph created largely or purely by wielding his power and entitlement. The reading makes it evident that people, already hard-hit by the famine, had to go through an internal crisis by selling of their livelihood to safeguard their lives. To make the psychological state of the poor worse, they were able to see the treatment to the priestly and administrative class was

completely the opposite. These classes were exempted from giving up their privileges, a tragic irony! In other words: When people come for help to the leadership because they know that there are actually enough resources to go around for everyone, then the leadership would tell the people to dig deep into their own resources, even if it means through exploitative labour!

It is clear from the passage that the situation was best set out for radical hospitality. It is also a test of Joseph's leadership perspective and how he understands the life of his community, and not just his own, of the Pharaoh's and/or of the privileged class.

Joseph collected all the money to be found in the land of Egypt and in the land of Canaan, in exchange for the grain that they bought; and Joseph brought the money into Pharaoh's house.

Joseph's understanding of citizenship of the commons, of the welfare of the citizens during the times of crisis, of the welfare perspective that the state must be taking safeguard its citizens show a detached nature of his leadership from his responsibility when he was given freedom to carve a life-centred economic policy. Joseph was clear that he would safeguard the Pharaoh and the ruling class including the priestly class. He did not see in the citizens as his neighbours, nor showed a sense of love in his responsibility. Emmanuel Levinas says: 'Love your neighbour, he is like you . . . Love your neighbour; the work of loving is for the reason you yourself . . . Would you say this is an extremely audacious reading?' Levinas goes on to say that our notions of love could get patronising and charitable if we did not love people for their personhood and for their subjectivity. This calls for a very cautious and critical reading of today's passage.

Our economy must be rooted in our understandings of sacraments

Here is a call from an am'nesic (*amnesia*) mind to an anamnestic practice (anamnesis). All our ministerial activities, theological

reflections and field work are 'immersions' in real contexts of our days. These immersions are what I call *baptismal* or *sacramental*. Recalling Jesus' notions of baptism is important here. Not surprisingly Jesus tells the sons of Zebedee (Mark 10): It is not about the positions of power but about remembering what your baptismal and eucharistic calls are. It is to know and remember that we are to be baptized in the baptism of Jesus and to drink from the cup that Jesus drank from. It is in this 'remembering' that there is 're-mem-bering' those who are deliberately or otherwise kept away from our theologies, spiritualities and the ideologies behind our field-work. The crisis that Joseph created removed people from the realm and thought-process of the leadership. By keeping people away, Joseph effectively kept the God of the people away.

It was during my Bachelor of Divinity (BD) days that I came across a book that gave a basic shape to my understanding of economy and theology. The book is *God the Economist: The Doctrine of God and Political Economy* by Douglas Meeks. Summarily, the church has separated God from economy. Sadly, even the livelihood of common masses is kept away from the practices of modern economy. Therefore, there is a compelling need to correlate theology and modern economy, where there is deliberate forgetfulness of the poor and the unrepresented. Meeks' work critically reviews the absence of God when common masses suffer but then God somehow magically appears to help the powerful! Biblically, there is enough to go around for everyone if we wish to keep it that way. In such circumstances, Trinitarian formula of sharing the essence of life as the core of economy of life.

The amnesia or forgetfulness of Joseph of his own past of being abandoned, ignored and left to die is for us to bear in mind. He forgot his earlier roots of slavery. His own experiences should have grounded his policies well in the needs of the suffering

masses. But he went on to make them slaves. He became a slave-master. Through the Pentateuch, there is the divine voice bringing us to the reality and reminding us “Remember that you were once slaves.”

Take the sides of the underprivileged

Only the land of the priests he did not buy; for the priests had a fixed allowance from Pharaoh, and lived on the allowance that Pharaoh gave them; therefore, they did not sell their land.

The priestly class in the passage is a class of entitled people, pampered by the state and leadership. They are disconnected from the suffering, pain and death of people. The crisis does not seem to have affected them as Joseph made sure to not let them suffer. They were immune to everything that is happening around them. History tells us that the Egyptian priesthood was already placed by Pharaoh upon an independent and separate basis. Only the kings and priests and the military (who held lands of the king) were considered as landowners. It is also recorded that “the greatest and best part of the land was in the possession of the priests” (Jacobus). They had daily rations from the king. Thus, they had no occasion to sell their land, though it was rendered useless by the famine. Then there is Joseph, who is married to Aseneth, the daughter of an Egyptian priest. This marriage further strengthens Joseph’s allegiance to the priestly class and to Pharaoh.

It helps us recall the main cause of French revolution; the unequal French society, especially the way the priestly class had colluded with the ruling class: There was saying that captured the working system of the French society: ‘The nobles fight, the clergy pray, and the people pay.’

When that year was ended, they came to him the following year, and said to him, ‘We cannot hide from my lord that our money is all

spent; and the herds of cattle are my lord's. There is nothing left in the sight of my lord but our bodies and our lands.

Here the language of helplessness and submission, which will secretly please the leadership and gives them a sense of gratification, is eerily loud. Now we wonder what the priestly class were doing for the entire year, the 'class of the Lordship.' Do not blame if your mind already wandered around your respective churches and institutions! Let the Spirit speak and work in us.

Joseph and the priestly class would have been pleased by the perspective of Tolstoy. But If Joseph were a ruler during the times of Martin Luther and carried out his so-called reforms, Luther would be vexed by Joseph's ideas. As a cryptic message from his work *On the Freedom of a Christian*, Luther would have told Joseph: "A Christian is a perfectly free lord of all, subject to none. A Christian is a perfectly dutiful servant of all, subject of all, subject to all." Luther's paradoxical teaching of Christian freedom, following Christ and St. Paul, joins 'lordship' and 'servanthood' in one person. The Lordship, for Luther, is a radically different Lordship expressed in Christ, which contested the ecclesial ideas of Lordship of his times or the Lordship over huge real estates with bonded labourers like Joseph did, or like the medieval church did. Just look around ourselves to see more modern versions of such Lordships. Luther would go on to say: For Christ, love binds him as an utterly dutiful servant to the neighbour, subject to everyone. The paradox of Christian freedom then plays out in faith and love. Luther sees all things in Christ, His person and work as He applies His saving effects to the Christian.

To conclude, we do well to see in the Bible that it is in the meeting of those who are strangers or made strangers in their own land that God extends the covenantal life, the life that upholds and sustains a community. This covenantal calling also calls for a proactive way of working towards fullness of life.

4

JESUS, THE GREAT MAHABALI

A REFLECTION BASED ON JOHN 19:25-30

Johnson Thomaskutty¹

The crucifixion of Jesus under Pontius Pilate was one of the historically certain and theologically pregnant events in human history. Probably originating with the Assyrians and Babylonians, crucifixion was used systematically by the Persians in the sixth century BCE. Alexander the Great introduced it to the eastern Mediterranean countries in the fourth century BCE, and Phoenicians introduced it to Rome in the third century BCE.² The Romans performed crucifixion for 500 years until it was abolished by Constantine I in the fourth century CE. It was applied mostly to slaves, disgraced soldiers, Christians and foreigners and only very rarely to Roman citizens.³

In spite of its cruelty as a form of punishment, crucifixion was practiced throughout the ancient world. The act itself damaged no vital organs, nor did it result in excessive bleeding. Death came slowly, sometimes after several days, through shock or a painful process as the muscles used in breathing suffered increasingly. The person was usually denied burial and the body was left on the cross to serve as food to the birds or to rot. Naked and affixed to a stake, cross or tree, the victim was subjected to suffer ridicule by frequent passerby. In a worldly sense, Jesus underwent such a disgraceful death on the cross.

1 Dr. Johnson Thomaskutty is Professor of New Testament at The United Theological College, Bengaluru.

2 <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/14750495/>, accessed on 2nd September 2023.

3 <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/14750495/>, accessed on 2nd September 2023.

In John 19, the death of Jesus on the cross is vividly portrayed. The Greek word *stauros* can either mean 'a stake' or 'a cross.' The verbal form used is *stauroō* means 'to fix stakes,' 'to crucify,' 'to mortify,' and 'to make a sacrifice.' While the Synoptic evangelists pay much attention on the resurrection of Jesus, John prepares his audience right from the beginning toward the death of Jesus. Death of Jesus on the cross is given much significance within the overall framework of the Fourth Gospel. In the context of the Onam tradition, the ideal and righteous king Mahabali sacrificed his life as a public servant of the people of Kerala. While Mahabali's sacrifice can be considered as a local manifestation, Jesus's sacrifice can be considered as an event with a universal impact.

The narrator uses certain catchwords to pay attention toward the cross and the death of Jesus. The first catchword is 'the hour of the Son of Man.' In John 2:4; 4:21, 23; 4:52-53; 7:6, 8, 30; and 8:20, Jesus states that the hour has not yet come. But, in 12:23 and 13:1, Jesus states that the hour of the Son of Man has come. This is all about the *hora*, the hour of Jesus, for him to be crucified. The second expression is 'the lifting up of the Son of Man' (John 3:13-14; 8:28; 12:32-34). The Greek expression *hupsōsen* means 'raising up,' 'lifting up,' or performing at an elevated space. This is another significant expression to indicate the death of Jesus on the cross. It is not at all talking about the resurrection of Jesus, but about Jesus's death on the cross.

The third expression is 'the glorification of the Son of Man.' Jesus is being glorified through his very death on the cross. In that sense, cross is the symbol of Jesus's *hour* of divine mission; his *lifting up* on the cross as a fulfilment of *missio Dei*; and his glorification in order to reveal the divine virtues in the world. *Stauros* or the 'cross of Jesus' is symbolically the ultimate mission point of Jesus in this world and before the God of heavens. Now,

let us examine the four utterances of the Johannine Jesus from the cross.

'Dear woman, here is your son' (v. 26)

Jesus's mother appears twice in the Gospel of John: first, in 2:1-5, at the outset of Jesus's public ministry, where she attends the wedding at Cana most probably of one of her closest relatives; and second, in 19:25-27, at the close of Jesus's public ministry, where she appears alongside of her sister, Mary the wife of Clopas, Mary Magdalene, and the Beloved Disciple. In both the cases, Jesus addresses her as 'woman' (*gunai*), not as 'mother' (*mētera*). While the narrator introduces her as Jesus's mother, Jesus addresses her as 'woman.' It is not out of disrespect Jesus addresses her as 'woman.' The word *gunai* or *gunē* can mean 'a woman,' 'a married woman,' or 'a wife.' Jesus respected her as his worldly mother as in both the cases he addresses her as 'dear woman.' After introducing Mary in 2:1-5, the narrator was silent about her until 19:25-26. That means, Mary was silently following Jesus throughout the public ministry. Jesus's care for Mary is foregrounded in 19:26. While the brothers of Jesus were mostly unbelievers as it is indicated in 7:1-10, Jesus does not want to entrust the believing mother under their care. As the Father Joseph does not show any tenet of believing, Jesus does not want to entrust the mother under Joseph's care too. Even there would have been a possibility of Joseph's death by then.

Jesus finds an appropriate person to take care of his earthly mother. Who was none other than the Beloved Disciple. Jesus says to Mary: "Dear woman, here is your son." The expression *ho huios sou* can mean 'here is your own son' or 'consider the one who is standing here as your own son.' Even at the point of death on the cross, Jesus was caring his worldly mother. As the evangelist John depicts each character and events representatively to affirm a universal fact, this event cannot be

considered as an isolated event. It demonstrates the universal care of Jesus. Here, the cross stands out as a symbol of universal care of Jesus. Jesus risks or sacrifices his own life for others. All those who are afflicted, isolated, uncared, and dehumanized can receive eternal care under the cross of Jesus. The dehumanized and ostracized women in Manipur and different parts of India, the bruised Dalits of the nation, and ill-treated tribal and Adivasi communities in different parts of this great nation can find solace under the cross of Jesus.

‘Here is your mother’ (v. 27)

In the Fourth Gospel, this is Jesus’s second utterance from the cross. Jesus utters to the Beloved Disciple: “Here is your mother.” The expression *hē mētēr sou* can mean ‘here is your own mother’ or ‘consider her as your own mother.’ In John’s Gospel, the Beloved Disciple is almost always considered as a representative character. While Jesus is demonstrated as the ‘Ideal Teacher,’ the ‘Beloved Disciple’ is demonstrated as an ‘Ideal Disciple.’ While Joseph’s unavailability is obvious and his brothers’ unbelieving nature is conspicuous, the Beloved Disciple is demonstrated as a key figure. Jesus’s wider family as the children of God (*tekna*; 1:12) and as friends (*philoï*; 15:14) is foregrounded through the virtue of believing in Jesus. In that sense, the Beloved Disciple was an ideal figure whom Jesus entrusts his most precious earthly belonging.

Jesus entrusts Mary under the care of the Beloved Disciple. Jesus hands over the ‘best of his life’ to the best person whom he found in the world. For Jesus, ‘believing’ in God/Jesus is the criterion: first, Jesus was concerned of Mary not merely because of her status as ‘mother,’ but because of her status as a believer and a follower throughout the public ministry; second, Jesus did not entrust Mary upon the care of his brothers. It was mainly because of their status as ‘unbelieving’ people; and third,

rather than entrusting his believing mother under the care of his unbelieving brothers, Jesus entrusts his believing mother under the care of a believing disciple, who is none other than the Beloved Disciple.

As a believer, the Beloved Disciple receives a new and additional responsibility. Here, cross stands out as a symbol from where people can access new responsibilities, missional engagements, and ministerial involvements. For the Beloved Disciple, having the mother of Jesus with him was one of the unique opportunities in the world. Just as the heavenly parent gave away Jesus to save the universe (3:16), Jesus gives away his precious person to someone else. Just as Jesus lavished his superabundant generosity, we are supposed to lavish our care and generosity in a world where there is scarcity, inequality, poverty, and struggle-some lives.

'I am thirsty' (v. 28)

Jesus is thirsty on the cross. John's Gospel is nicknamed as a 'Gospel of Water.' There are multifarious indications about water throughout the Gospel. Pharisees ask John the Baptist: "Why then do you baptize?" (1:25); John the Baptist responds to the Jews: "I baptize with water" (1:26); Jesus turns water into wine (2:1-11); Jesus says to Nicodemus: "Unless you born by water and Spirit" (3:1-10); Jesus and his disciples are involved in baptism (3:22-26); Jacob's well is introduced by the narrator and Jesus offers living water to the Samaritan woman (4:1-42); the water of the pool of Bethesda (5:1-10); Jesus crosses the water of the Sea of Galilee (6:16-21); Jesus says: "If anyone is thirsty, let her/him come to me and drink" (7:37-38); the Pool of Siloam (9:1-41); washing the feet of the disciples (13:1-20); a sudden flow of water and blood from his body (19:34); and the disciples gather on the banks of the Sea of Galilee (21:1-10). Right from the beginning till the end, we see a lot of evidences concerning water in the Fourth Gospel.

The irony of the Gospel is that in a Gospel of abundant waters, Jesus is thirsty. Jesus says: "I am thirsty." The Greek expression *dipsō* means an 'ardent thirst.' Instead of giving water to the thirsty Jesus, as it is indicated in 19:34: "one of the soldiers pierced his side with a spear, bringing a sudden flow of blood and water." Instead of giving water to an ardent thirsty Jesus, the world dropped out even the last drops of water from his body. Symbolically, cross is a place of all sufferings of God's Beloved one for people's good. Cross is a mark of Jesus's ardent thirst for eternal comfort and satisfaction. Jesus's ardent thirst was far beyond his physical thirst. A thirst for justice in the world; a thirst for righteousness among humanity; a thirst for eternal bliss in the universe; and a thirst for human transformation and liberation. The one who is able to provide living water is thirsty on the cross; the one who is able to turn water into wine is drinking wine on the cross. As Jesus dies as an ardently thirsty person, his thirst was for human emancipation and rejuvenation.

'It is finished' (v. 30)

The Greek expression used here is *tetelestai*, which means "It is done," "It is finished," "It is fulfilled," and "It is accomplished." When Indian cricket players like Sachin Tendulkar or Virat Kohli beat sixers, they make unusual howling and sounds alongside of other teammates. They create huge sound to celebrate the event: Hurrah! When football players kick goals, they create an unusual sound and celebrate the event. Jesus accomplishes a huge task and shouts a universally significant utterance: *Tetelestai!* In reality, what Jesus accomplished/finished on the cross: first, Jesus accomplished the will of the Heavenly God; second, Jesus accomplished the Law of Moses; third, Jesus accomplished the ceremonial sacrifices on the cross; fourth, Jesus finished the powers of sin, Satan, and death; fifth, Jesus poured out or finished his own blood on the cross; sixth, Jesus finished the mission of the Heavenly God in the world; and seventh, Jesus accomplished

all the covenants and became the final covenant. Cross is the symbol or mark of Jesus's accomplishment in the world below. As Jesus accomplishes a universally significant task with eternal effect, he shouts from the cross *Tetelestai!*

Jesus accomplished the task of the Heavenly God on the cross of Calvary. The task was liberative and transformative in action. The eternal sacrifice of Jesus brought a universal impact. All the sorrows, dehumanisations, ostracizations, and shackles of the world are put at an end on the cross of Jesus. The Dalits, tribals, ostracized women, Adivasis, and all other suffering humanity can come under the cross of Jesus and receive freedom, care, responsibility, and eternal liberation.

Concluding Remarks

The *stauros* marks the hour of the Son of Man, lifting up of the Son of Man, and glorification of the Son of Man. Under the cross, people received eternal care; under the cross, people received new responsibilities. As a thirsty person, Jesus comforts the people of the world and provides them eternal satisfaction. Jesus's thirst was for human liberation and transformation. On the cross, Jesus accomplishes the will of the Heavenly God. The *stauros*, the cross of Jesus, is a symbol of eternal care, abundant responsibilities, everlasting satisfaction, and universal accomplishment. Let us come closer to the cross of Jesus. Let us invite others and draw them nearer to the cross of Jesus. As Paul the Apostle par-excellence proclaimed, let us say together "we preach Christ the crucified."

Jesus exercised his heavenly freedom with responsibilities. Jesus's life and ministry can be considered as a paradigm for us to exercise our freedom in Christ with responsibilities. Our mission in the world is sacrificial and hence a *mahabali*. We are supposed to live a life for 'others.' Just as Mahabali, the ancient King of Kerala, was a paradigm of self-sacrifice

and just as Jesus was a Great Mahabali for all walks of people irrespective of all human-made boundaries, we are supposed to give our life as a living sacrifice for the good of 'others.' This message is paramount in the context of growing tendencies of self-centredness, majoritarian politics that subsides the 'other,' Christian persecution in the state of Manipur and other parts of India, and the dehumanizing tendencies toward the Dalit, tribal, Adivasi and other vulnerable communities in our nation. In a context in which 'ours' is prioritized over against the 'other,' the model of Mahabali in Kerala and Jesus in the universal context prioritize the 'other' over against 'ours.' Thus, Jesus's death on the cross can be considered as a Great Sacrifice or a *Mahabali* with a universal impact. AMEN.

5

RECLAIMING THE DIGNITY OF CHILDREN

Aravind Jeyakumar Moniraj¹

The month of November is always a special month for children since there are so many days to celebrate—The World Sunday School Day falls on November 7, the National Children’s Day is celebrated on November 14 and November 20 was marked as World Children’s Day by UNICEF. All these days dedicated to children signify the need of promoting and advocating the rights of children in today’s complex context across the globe. The first Sunday of November is traditionally celebrated as World Sunday School Day across the globe marking the beginning of the Sunday School Movement. The idea of Sabbath School or Sunday School for poor uneducated children began in England in the 18th century. It was in the year 1780, a person named Robert Raikes of Gloucester in England has devised a plan to gather poor and uneducated working children into education classes on Sundays. Clean clothes and learning materials were provided and instruction given in reading, writing, hygiene and good citizenship. This was publicised in Raikes own journal *Gloucester Journal* in 1783 which gained more popularity.

The churches hoped that this effort would serve the dual purpose of bettering the future of society and reducing the rampant criminal actions done by children (i.e., minor crime,

¹ Dr. Aravind Jeyakumar Moniraj is the Associate Professor and Head of the Department of Old Testament Studies in Gurukul Lutheran Theological College & Research Institute, Chennai, Tamil Nadu.

committed by young people). Although, neither evangelism nor religious training were the expressed goals of the new schools, there was the hope that the morality taught, being based on the truths of Scripture, might bring about a transformation in the hearts of the children. And thus, with this main objective the Sabbath or Sunday school was born. Later, by the early 1800's, the goals of the Sunday schools were changing. The Sunday Schools were seen as a place and an opportunity to teach the gospel and Christian doctrine to children. This led to the formation of the World Sunday School Union in 1803 and the Sunday School Movement rapidly spread across the globe. In fact, many secular schools which were established for children's education concentrated on imparting Christian religious instructions as well.

The India Sunday School Union ISSU was formed in January 1876 at a conference of eight missionary bodies at Allahabad under the leadership of T. J. Scott, a Methodist minister and educator. In fact, there are also other evidences to say that in India, Sunday school was founded by the Serampore Trio William Carey, Joshua Marshman, and William Ward and specially under the initiative of Marshman in Calcutta in the year of 1800 who wanted to shape the children community after seeing thousands of children who neither go to school nor to Church. The early CMS missionaries who came to Kerala began teaching the Bible to children and therefore, it was evident that systematic Sunday School work started in 1880 at Mallappally. Therefore, Sunday School Movement has a long and rich history in India as well. Today the contribution of Sunday School in the holistic growth of our children are enormous.

Children's Day, celebrated on November 14, is recognized across India to increase awareness of the rights, care, and education of children. The day is also held as a tribute to India's First Prime Minister, Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru. Fondly

known as “Chacha Nehru” among children, he advocated for children to have fulfilled education. Nehru considered children as the real strength of a nation and foundation of society. The nation usually celebrates Children’s Day with educational and motivational programs held across India, by and for children. Similarly, World Children’s Day which was first established in 1954 as Universal Children’s Day and is celebrated on November 20, each year to promote international togetherness, awareness among children worldwide, and improving children’s welfare. November 20 is an important date as it is the date in 1959 when the UN General Assembly adopted the Declaration of the Rights of the Child. It is also the date in 1989 when the UN General Assembly adopted the Convention on the Rights of the Child. Since 1990, World Children’s Day also marks the anniversary of the date that the UN General Assembly adopted both the Declaration and the Convention on children’s rights. World Children’s Day offers each of us an inspirational entry-point to advocate, promote and celebrate children’s rights, translating into dialogues and actions that will build a better world for children.

In spite of observing such special days for children in order to preserve their rights still the entire world is striving for a better future for every child. The moto of UNICEF (United Nations International Children’s Emergency Fund) is “Every child has the right to live free from violence, exploitation and abuse.” But in contrast, today children worldwide suffer deceptive forms of violence, exploitation and abuse. Violence against children knows no boundaries. It happens in every country, and in the places, children should be most protected—their homes, schools and online. It can be physical, emotional or sexual. And in most cases, children experience violence at the hands of the people they trust. Children in humanitarian settings are especially vulnerable. During armed conflict, natural disasters and other emergencies, children may be forced to flee their homes, some torn from their families and exposed to exploitation and abuse

along the way. They may be injured or killed by explosive weapons in conflict, or recruited by armed forces. Especially for girls and women, the threat of gender-based violence is innumerable. Harmful cultural practices pose another grave risk to girls and boys worldwide. Hundreds of millions of girls have been subjected to child marriage and female genital mutilation.

A global survey which was conducted to identify the terrible issues that children face worldwide shows ten alarming situations that children are forced to face and they are: first, violence through indoctrination—in some parts of the world, children from one community is taught to hate the other community and violence, death and child martyrdom were taught and falsely projected as essential part of their religion and culture; second, poverty—according to UNICEF's report, 25,000 children die each day due to poverty; third, life as refugees—of the more than 50 million refugees and displaced people in the world, approximately half are children; fourth, lack of access to education—more than 100 million children across the globe have no access to school and there are more than 150 million school dropouts; fifth, child neglect—there are more children who are neglected by their families and communities and they face more devastations in all levels; sixth, child labour—it is estimated that more than 211 million children between the ages of 5 and 14 are working around the world and 120 million are working full time to support their impoverished families; seventh, child prostitution—according to the survey of UNICEF, children in prostitution under the age of 18 are steadily increasing across the globe; eighth, internet child pornography—knowingly or unknowingly the virtual world addiction leads children to victims of pornography and online violence; ninth, child trafficking and slavery—child trafficking is the fastest growing means by which children are forced to slavery, a global report says more than 1.3 million children are in forced labour situation as a result of child trafficking; and tenth, military use of children— children are singled out and recruited

by both armed forces and armed opposition groups; more than 250,000 children under the age of 18 are into armed forces. This is an alarming survey which reminds us that children across the globe are still at risk and the entire humanity has failed to advocate their rights and still not able to create a better future for them.

In the recent years many images of children drew national and international attention, which depicted the plight of children in our unsafe world. The first incident is about a young boy found lying face-down on a beach near Turkish resort of Bodrum who was one of at least 12 Syrians who drowned attempting to reach Greece in September 2015. The second incident is with regard to Asifa Banu an eight-year-old Muslim girl child who was kidnapped, brutally raped and murdered in Kathua, Kashmir in January 2018. Another incident is about a migrant woman pulling a suitcase with her child sleeping half hung on it on the Agra highway during the novel coronavirus-induced lockdown in May 2020. The fourth about a seventeen-year-old girl who committed suicide since she was sexually assaulted by her own school teacher in Coimbatore, Tamilnadu. All these disturbing images show that the entire humanity has to take responsibility for such unpleasant things happening against children. We and our entire system have failed to create a better world where they will live safely without any violence done against them. In such a perplexed context how we as a faith community are going to create a better world and reclaim the dignity of children is the Himalayan challenge that we have today! Let us march towards that goal of reclaiming the dignity of children in the light of a biblical passage from the Gospel according to St. Mark 10:13-16.

People were bringing little children to him in order that he might touch them; and the disciples spoke sternly to them. But when Jesus saw this, he was indignant and said to them, "Let the little children come to me; do not stop them; for it is to such as these that the

kingdom of God belongs. Truly I tell you, whoever does not receive the kingdom of God as a little child will never enter it." And he took them up in his arms, laid his hands on them, and blessed them.

Traditionally, Mark 10:13-16 is understood as Jesus announcing "God's reign coming as a gift and as an experience into which one can enter only if he or she has the receptiveness of a child"—therefore, the ancient interpreters understood that "the receptiveness of a child" was the key for understanding the analogy between the phrase "as a little child" and "receiving the kingdom of God." Moreover, traditionally the focus was on "the characteristics of children" as the key to the meaning of this passage. However, in the last decade, many commentators have analysed the meaning of the phrase "as a little child" in Mark 10:15 and argued that Mark 10:13-16 must be seen in light of Mark 9:33-37 and that both of these references to a child depict not primarily on assumed characteristics of children but rather on their social status in the first-century world: first, Jesus' saying in Mark 10:15 is not formulated on any idealistic notion of children; second, rather the child in Mark 10:13-16 and 9:36-37 represents another category of those marginalized and dominated (like women, the poor, and the unclean); third, the child was, in fact, the "least" in familial and societal structures; fourth, children were easily dominated and exploited because of their vulnerability, dependent as they were on adults; fifth, Jesus is thus inviting his disciples into a new reality of community and family, where the "least" becomes the model for discipleship; and sixth, this means that the disciple should take up the powerlessness and vulnerability of the child.

This passage (Mark 10:13-16) can be further divided into three parts: the opening part sets the stage for Jesus' speech and action (10:13); the central part includes two sayings of Jesus prompted by his strong displeasure with his disciples (10:14-15); and the final part stresses Jesus' action (10:16). Based on this passage the

following subsections are formulated in order to ponder over the theme of reclaiming the dignity of children under three subtitles.

Let children be treated as children with respect

Two things are mentioned in the opening part (i.e., Mark 10:13), which depict a conflict. On the one hand, some people were bringing little children to Jesus “in order that he might touch them.” In that time and place, children had very little status. In that sense, they were like many of the other people or people in the ‘so-called’ marginal status (lepers, women, tax collectors) whom Jesus favoured. But on the other hand, the disciples expressed strong disapproval of what they were doing. Directly or indirectly, they said “don’t disturb the teacher” shh . . . Certainly the Markan readers at this point would have been reminded of Mark 9:33-37 where Jesus embraced a little child and announced, “Whoever receives one such child in my name receives me; and whoever receives me receives not me but the one who sent me.” The disciples have obviously not learned the lesson of discipleship which involves welcoming the “least ones.” Indeed, they wilfully oppose Jesus’ conception of God’s reign (Mark 8:33). In order to reclaim the dignity of children there should be a change in attitude among the elders. The attitude of the disciples was so rude and unpleasant or in other words it was dominative which undermined and belittled the significance of children. They were with the opinion that children were disturbing elements and hindrance for Jesus’ ongoing conversation with the elders. A perspectival change should take place among elders to see things from the perspective of children. Since children were marginalized and vulnerable, the disciples overpowered them with their dominant attitude when they approached Jesus and they were not respected since they were not equal to adults. Let us respect children who are also created in the image and likeness of God and value them. In spite of all the disciplinary schemas that we have formulated to mould

children we should not neglect or underestimate them which is in fact a terrible crime happening against them across the globe.

Let us become the voice for the vulnerable children

Having no status or power, children can contribute nothing to Jesus' movement. They are neither worthy opponents nor worthy disciples. Being aware of all these things in the second part, i.e., in vv. 14-15, Jesus expresses strong emotional reaction to the rude action of his disciples and emphasizes two things. In 10:14 the narrative describes Jesus as becoming indignant (or, as the Greek word suggests, "becoming incensed at what is wrong") when he saw the disciples rudely rebuking the people bringing little children—in other words Jesus was not only incensed but he was totally disturbed by the way how his disciples were treating little children. This leads to two sayings of Jesus. The first one in 10:14 is specifically addressed to what the disciples have just done. Jesus' saying includes an initial positive exhortation that makes clear what the disciples are to do—"allow the little children to come to me"; next a prohibition that indicates what they are to cease doing—"do not continue stopping them!" and lastly the reason for both—"because of such ones is the kingdom of God." Now for the first time Jesus directly associates the kingdom of God with little children.

Connecting the kingdom of God and children prepares for Jesus' second saying that is solemnly introduced with the words mentioned in 10:15 "Truly I say to all of you." The same phrase is also used with all the linguistic similarities in Jesus' saying mentioned in 9:37. Both begin with Greek words that are translated "whoever," both use the Greek word "receive," both are concerned with a little child. Moreover, both serve as the final and culminating saying in their narrative episodes. Even more importantly, Jesus' saying in 10:15 completes the logic begun in his earlier saying in Mark 9. Receiving a little

child in Jesus' name, according to 9:37, is equated with receiving Jesus himself and even God ("the one who sent me"). This is in fact a new theology of God child or Christ child as the foundation of children's rights—because God became a child. This assertion is conceptually bound to the conviction that God became incarnate in a human being. The implications of this non-negotiable element of creedal Christianity have rarely been underscored. In this respect the teaching of Jesus is confirmed, not by his teaching about children, but by the church's teaching about Jesus, that He is God incarnate, and so God the Child. In addition, this theological claim appears similar to that of Matt 25:31-46—by practicing hospitality and care for the least and most vulnerable human being, one receives Jesus who on God's behalf is in solidarity with this "least one." Mark 10:15 furthers the logic by inviting the follower of Jesus to enter the sphere of Jesus and God by entering the place and plight of a little child, one quite vulnerable and totally dependent on benevolent care and protection of adults.

As we all know, each contextual theology has arisen from a particular social location and has offered a critique of conventional ways of doing theology. Liberation theology began the trend with its "preferential option for the poor;" working in "base communities" it discerned in Scripture—God on the side of the poor, thus empowering the oppressed and challenging society, as well as the church, with this particular biblical hermeneutic. Therefore, in contextual theologies both the oppressed and those who advocate human rights work together for the upliftment of the suppressed communities. However, in Child Theology, the theology which advocates the rights of children, a child is not in the same way its own protagonist like in other contextual liberation theologies, rather it appears to be also an adult advocating the rights of children and establishing justice for their better future. This is more evident in Jesus' reaction when the children who approached him were belittled by his

disciples—Jesus was literally disturbed and became the voice of the voiceless children when they were deeply humiliated by his disciples. Likewise, Jesus demands his disciples today to give voice to the vulnerable children who are suffering across the globe due to the selfishness motives of individuals and the geopolitical issues!

Let us make this world a comfort zone for children

Mark 10:13-16 ends by describing Jesus' action and I love this verse because it records Jesus' demonstration of his preaching: And he (Jesus) took them up in his arms, laid his hands on them, and blessed them. His action embodies the dynamic of God's kingdom: welcoming and blessing the children epitomize God's gracious reception of the vulnerable and needy. Moreover, Jesus' action vanished the psychological agony that was caused by the rudeness of his disciples and ultimately created a space of comfort zone for the children to celebrate their life without any fear. We do not know a great deal about children in the first-century Mediterranean world. Existing literary documents (including the New Testament), however, do allow us to assume some things about adult attitudes towards children and the actual circumstances of children's lives. Clearly both the Palestinian Jewish society and the larger Greco-Roman world were patriarchal, in which male offspring were valued more highly than female ones. Roman law did not prohibit the exposure of babies, especially females, as a means of ridding a father of an unwanted infant. In contrast to our contemporary idea of childhood, the number of years for childhood was few, with girls promised and given in marriage by mid-teens, boys only somewhat later. Crucially important to the father of the household was the marriageability of young daughters as a means of extending and improving the honour and financial security of his family. A father's son extended the family lineage and control over a trade or land that was owned. Peasant families with less

or no land holdings undoubtedly needed both young sons and daughters to contribute quickly to the family work force. Some scholars have suggested that harsh economic disruptions (and possibly divorce) could create a need for a family's abandoning children or selling them into slavery.

Centuries have gone but still the plight of children (esp. girl children) is still the same. Although we strongly affirm along with the action of Jesus and the motto UNICEF that "Every child has the right to live free from violence, exploitation and abuse," still there are millions of children who face numerous struggles as it was stated in the survey which was presented during the beginning of this reflection. If we claim that our world is a comfort zone for children, then why we are still witnessing the terrible issues faced by children such as poverty, life as refugees, lack of access to education, child labour, child prostitution, child trafficking and slavery, violence through indoctrination and military use of children. There are inequalities that still exist—some children are privileged and some are not; some are living in a peaceful atmosphere but not all; moreover, due to wars and global pandemic the life of numerous children was devastated. How do we treat children with physical and mental challenges and health issues? How safe our homes are for our own children? Are the schools and institutions function as comfort zones for our children?

Let us break the silence and repent for our actions which have made this world still not a comfort zone for the children across the globe. Let us be resuscitated by the Spirit of God to change this condition by following the footsteps of Jesus Christ in reclaiming the dignity of children. On the one hand, "receiving the kingdom *as a little child*" implies the welcome and blessing of Jesus for us as we recognize ourselves to be as vulnerable and needy as a little child. Inclusion in God's kingdom is absolute gift. Yet, on the other hand, the kingdom also invites responsible

action on our part. By embracing a little vulnerable child, we are welcoming Jesus (and thus God) and receiving the kingdom. *“Receive the Kingdom of God when it approaches in the form of a vulnerable child.”* Amen.

6

THE VOICE OF SILENCE

D. S. Ben Das¹

Silence, or *mauna*, refers to the practice of not speaking, and one who does this regularly is called *muni*. While not-speaking is an important part of *mauna*, or silence, it is much more than that. Silencing oneself does not mean not-speaking or inactivity; it is restricting speech and actions. Wise people restrict their words but speak a lot through their actions. According to Sri Ramaṇa Maharṣi, “Silence is the highest eloquence.” When we silence others, it is called subjugation, oppression, overpowering, authoritarianism, and the like. When we practice silence for ourselves, it empowers and strengthens us for the good of ourselves and others.

Different modern disciplines, such as psychology, anthropology, and others, have done well in their studies of silence. According to many academics, there are primarily nine different sorts of silence. Silence has great significance in Indian spirituality. Ādi Śankarācārya held that “Silence is the first door to spiritual eminence.” We see meaningful use of silence in the Bible as well. Silence is a very vast topic to be pondered. There is so much to be understood and practiced that cannot be addressed in this limited time. So let us briefly meditate on “The Voice of Silence” through the Bible and Indian scriptures.

¹ Rev. Dr. D. S. Ben Das is Associate Professor of Religion and PRO of The United Theological College, Bengaluru, India.

Silence: The mighty presence of God (1 Kings 19:11-13)

1 Kings Chapter 19 narrates the Flee of Elijah from Jezebel. While Elijah was lying down under the broom tree, an angel fed him twice. Then he went in the strength of that food for forty days and forty nights to Horeb, the Mount of God. At that place, he went to a cave and spent the night there. There, God spoke to Elijah. God told him to 'go out and stand on the mountain before the Lord, for the Lord is about to pass by.' Elijah went out of the cave and waited for God to pass by. Then there was a great wind, so strong that it was splitting mountains and breaking rocks in pieces, but God was not in the wind. After the wind, there was an earthquake, but God was not in the earthquake. After the earthquake, there was a fire, but God was not in the fire. And after the fire, there was a sound of sheer silence. That was the presence of God.

Here we see traditions in transformation. Wind, earthquake, and fire were traditionally seen as manifestations of divine presence, but here those are reduced to mere precursors of a mysterious 'sound of fine silence.' Beyond the traditional conceptions of God's revelation, in the given incident, the presence of God was in silence, in the sound of sheer silence.

Making loud voices with drums, horns, musical instruments, and the human mouth are the methods of primal religions during their worship of God. They believe that only loud voices reach God, who stays far above the sky or mountains. Some primal communities believe that only when devotees make loud cries and voices will they get the attention of God, so that their prayers will be heard, their sacrifices will be received, and they will be blessed. Since all the established religions come from their primal stage, most of them still follow many of their primal characteristics, including making loud voices. Christianity is not an exception. At the so-called 'high spiritual' worships, we sing with loud music, clap flashy, and pray in high voice. We shout,

cry, and emotionally worship. Sometimes we criticise those who worship silently, thinking that only in a loud voice do we have the presence of God.

Elijah's incident poses in front of us other possibilities of God realization. Yes, the presence of God is experienced in silence as well. Silence allows us to notice things we overlook. The Mighty God comes to humans in silence! Silence allows us to hear things that are buried under the normal buzz of daily life. We need to re-frame our thought patterns about our methods of worship and spirituality.

Wind, earthquake, and fire revealed theophany in the past in different contexts and transformed many sceptics into believers. But for Elijah, they were only natural phenomena and did not carry any experiences of theophany. Elijah encounters a uniquely real presence of God—beautifully captured in the phrase 'a sound of sheer silence,' the only occurrence of this phrase in the OT. This reminds us of the unique methods of God realization in our lives. As God cannot be stereotyped, revelations of God also cannot be typecast. No one can negate the different possibilities of the revelation of God. We have to be ready and open to any possibilities of God realization. In the life of Elijah, the presence of God was experienced in silence. According to Maitri Upaniṣad, "There is something beyond our mind that abides in silence within our mind. It is the Supreme Mystery beyond thought." Let our mind and our subtle bodies rest upon that which abides in silence and not rest upon anything else.

Silence: A Powerful Response of Jesus (Matthew 26:63)

When Jesus was brought to the Sanhedrin, the high priest and the whole council were looking for false testimony against Jesus so that they might put him to death (v. 59). So, the plot was set against Jesus. What has to be done with Jesus was already decided, and for them, the trial was only a formality to be

performed. Though many false witnesses came forward, they found none. At last, two people came forward and said, “This fellow said, I am able to destroy the temple of God and to build it in three days.” Then the high priest stood up and asked Jesus, “Have you no answer? What is it that they testify against you?” But even at that time, Jesus was silent.

There are so many reasons for the silence of Jesus. According to the doctrine of *pratītya samudpāda* (dependent origination) of Buddhism, “if this exists, that exists; if this ceases to exist, that also ceases to exist.” This means that one action produces another action as its invariable consequence. According to *pratītya samudpāda*, our one action will lead to a long or unending chain of action. The chain of actions can be good or harmful. So, Buddhism teaches *yama* (rules of self-restraint) to help people reach *samiyama* or self-control. Self-restraint means to hold instinctive desires in check and refrain from giving full expression to them in conduct. It is an act of discarding the weaker thoughts and actions—the same thoughts and actions that drag us down—and doubling down on our positive and good actions. Buddhism encourages restraint over the eyes, ears, nose, tongue, and body.

When Jesus was undergoing trial, those who were against Jesus did not have anything concrete to raise against him, and that is why they were bringing false witnesses. They were trying to get something substantial enough to justify the death penalty. On hearing all such false witnesses and the questions of the chief priest, if Jesus had answered them, they would have caught Jesus by his words. The high priest calls on Jesus to answer these allegations in the hope that he will say something that can be used against him. His words would have been misinterpreted by them to benefit their agenda; arguments would have no use since they were all planned to kill Jesus. And the chain of speeches or arguments would have endangered his disciples as well. To avoid all such consequences, Jesus kept silent.

Embracing silence helps us settle into the present moment and quiet any racing thoughts. It helps to overcome emotional reactions and to adopt mature and rational decisions and reactions. The approach of Jesus is the same as stated by David in Psalm 38:12-14 “Those who seek my life lay their snares; those who seek to hurt me speak of ruin, and meditate treachery all day long. But I am like the deaf, I do not hear; like the mute, who cannot speak. Truly, I am like one who does not hear, and in whose mouth is no retort.”

When we continue reading this pericopé, we see that when Jesus was asked regarding his Messiah identity, Jesus answered, and Jesus’ answer gave Caiaphas, the high priest, a new cause for condemning him: the condemnation of blasphemy, which carried the death penalty as per the Leviticus law.

Answering everyone and everything will lead us to problems. As Jesus did during his trial, let silence be our powerful response. We need to practice the art of silence. Sometimes, silence saves our lives; silence gives us peace; silence preserves our wealth; silence secures our future; and silence costs anything.

Silence in Hindu Mārga (*Bhagavad Gīta* 2:9)

As most of us know, Bhagavad Gīta contains the discourse that occurred during the Kurukshetra war. It is a conversation between Arjuna and Kṛṣṇa. Arjuna asked Kṛṣṇa, who was the charioteer, to place his chariot in the midst of the two armies. Kṛṣṇa, having placed the chariot between the two armies, asked Arjuna to behold the Kurus. Having seen his kinsmen, Arjuna was so filled with compassion and sadness that he cast away his bow and arrows and slumped into the seat of the chariot. It is in this context that the second chapter of the Bhagavad Gīta starts.

While being the charioteer, Kṛṣṇa was also the counsellor of Arjuna in the war. In their conversation, Kṛṣṇa was encouraging Arjuna to fight against his kinsmen, who are on the opposite

side now. In verse 9, Arjuna honoured the words of Kṛṣṇa and wanted to obey them. But after thinking seriously over what Kṛṣṇa had said and applying his own mind to his thoughts, he came to the conclusion that war could result in providing him with an affluent kingdom, honour, and fame, but it would not wipe out his grief, worry, and misery. Therefore, it was not befitting for him to wage war. So, Arjuna speaks his mind in clear words: "I will not fight." Having declared his decision not to fight and having nothing more to say, Arjuna became silent. Later, in the proceeding part of Bhagavad Gīta, we see that his silent meditation empowered him to rise up for the mission and to carry out his dharma or duty with devotion.

Bhagavad Gīta is not interpreted on the basis of its verbal and peripheral meanings. The discourse in the Bhagavad Gīta has philosophical connotations, as does the silence Arjuna observed at the end of this conversation. According to Ramana Maharṣi, silence is the way to self-realization. Silence is the greatest teacher and the greatest power of knowing. Here, after listening to Kṛṣṇa, Arjuna was meditating upon his words in silence.

Vivéka, or inner discernment, is only possible when we observe silence rather than react at a vocal level. Without discernment as to what we say, there is no *vivéka*. Arjuna, after a few moments of silence, achieves *vivéka*, or inner discernment, and acts accordingly. Indian traditions have so much to say about silence. According to Indian teachings on self-realization, only through *mauna* can we enter the *guha*, or secret cavern of the heart, in which the entire universe dwells in its true luminous state.

Silence, or *mauna* has a significant role in Indian spiritual ways. According to it, the Divine Word and cosmic *mantra* starting with the *praṇava mantra*, i.e., OM, is the sound of silence that we can only enter into with a silent mind and receptive heart. Cosmic *māntric* vibrations are the sounds of universal

space, in which there is no friction or noise. This is the space of consciousness. Entering into that, all limitations of time, place, and person disappear.

As such, *Mauna*, or silence, is one of the key Yoga practices. In yoga practice, *mauna* is the foundation for *dhāraṇa*, or concentration. The yoga system of Patañjali details the practice of silence. If we do not have the silence of speech and mind, we cannot concentrate our attention or fix our gaze within.

Mauna is the basis for *dhyāna*, or meditation. *Mauna*, or silence, creates stability for the mind, an inner seat, or *antar āsana* for meditation. Silence of speech and mind is the basis for holding the reflective state of meditation, in which the mind becomes still like a mirror. This stage is called *Ācitta vṛtti nirodha*. Meditation in silence and silent meditation go together and give us inner peace.

Mauna is the basis of *samādhi*, the unitary state of pure consciousness, which literally takes away our speech, mind, and breath that are interconnected. If we are not made silent in speech and mind, we cannot reach *samādhi*. In regard to Indian medical systems like *Āyurveda* and Yoga Therapy, the practice of *mauna* helps heal the body, *prāṇa*, and mind. There is a lot to share from Indian sources on the observation of silence, but due to our time constraints, I am concluding my reflection here.

Conclusion

Silence of speech, speaking little, speaking kindly, speaking the truth, and others are among the best spiritual practises, and they form the foundation for a genuine *sādhana* in Indian spirituality. The voice of silence is inequitably strong, loud, and powerful. As we have seen in the life of Elijah, God reveals in silence; silence can be used powerfully in crises as Jesus did; and silence empowers us to the mission, as shown by Arjuna. Silence is not nothingness or void. It has a voice of its own. Psychologically,

silence can increase self-awareness and self-compassion and improve decision-making skills with improved mental clarity. Listening to the voice of silence is essential for our spiritual growth and peaceful living. An action-oriented silence, or, in other words, a self-restraint action, is what is needed for us to overcome present-day turbulence.

7

BRIDGING THE GAP BETWEEN SUNDAY TO MONDAY: THE SACRED-SECULAR DIVIDE

Aby Alexandar¹

All of us enjoy Sunday, where we can worship God, come together for fellowship, have special lunch, rest, outings, and the like. But on Monday morning, many of our faces go bleak and we may say “Oh Monday again”; we are tensed, and forced to go back to our offices, schools, or colleges. We may feel a situation, ‘I do not want to go, but I have to go.’ Can we reflect on this issue and find some answers? As we reflect, let me share a few questions for us to ponder.

-Is God more concerned with our ‘spiritual’ life, meaning our church worship, prayer, Bible study, being in Sunday School, and attending fellowships?

-Is it that, what we do on Sunday is ‘sacred’ and what we do from Monday through Friday ‘secular’?

-Is work merely a means of earning our livelihood and supporting the ministry?

-Can I worship God from 9 AM to 5 PM (during my office hours)?

-Is there any real meaning or purpose in my work?

¹ Dr. Aby Alexandar is the Assistant Executive Director at the Christian Institute of Management (CIM), Chennai. He has completed a M.Com., M.Div., and Ph.D. in Business Administration. He has co-edited *Basic Management Handbook* (2011), *Management Education in Theological Institutions* (2019), *Legal Handbook* (2021), and *Christian Management in a VUCA World* (2022).

In a day, we spend a minimum of eight hours in our workplace or studies. In today's corporate work life, it may even go up to sixteen hours of work a day. One-third, i.e., more than one-half of our productive lifetime we spend in our workplace. In this context, it would be meaningful to reflect on the significance of work/workplace, especially from God's perspective.

According to Hugh Whelchel, the word 'work' in different forms is mentioned more than 800 times in the Bible. It is used more than all the words used to express worship, praise, music, and singing combined. Os Hillman, in his study on work in the Gospels, points out that "of Jesus' hundred and thirty-two public appearances, in the New Testament, hundred and twenty-two were in the workplace. Of the fifty-two parables Jesus told, forty-five had a workplace context. Hence, God gave a lot of significance to work life and workplaces. Let us now meditate on the theology of work, and what should be our approach toward work.

Biblical perspective of work

As we look at the Biblical understanding of work, the first thing I would like to emphasize is that work is a Creation Mandate. Some people treat work as a curse that came out of the sin Adam committed. What we see in Gen. 3:17b is *cursed is the ground because of you, through painful toil you would eat of it all the days of your life*. This does not mean that labor or work is because of the curse of God on man, as he sinned. Conversely, one of the very purposes of creation itself is Work, i.e., God created man to work! *The Lord God took the man and put him in the Garden of Eden to 'work it' and take care of it* (Gen. 2:15). In the previous chapter we see that God made humans in God's image so that they will first, 'rule over' the fish of the sea and birds of the air, over the livestock, over all the earth, over all the creatures (1:26); and second, 'fill' the earth and 'subdue' it. The Hebrew word used for 'rule' is *radhah*, which means to nurture. As we see, human beings are created to

nurture and to take care of the entire universe. Thus, one of the very purposes of creation itself is to work.

The second thing I would like to mention is that, in addition to being the creation mandate, work is an act of worship. In the following paragraphs, I explain it with a Biblical principle and a Biblical concept. One of the principles that we see in the Bible is the ‘all your heart principle.’ The Bible asks us to do two things with all our hearts. We are commanded to *Love the Lord your God with ‘all your heart’ and with all your soul and with all your mind* (Matthew 22:36-37). That is to worship the Lord with all our hearts. There is one more thing that the Bible asks us to do with all our hearts. *Whatever you do, ‘work at it’ with ‘all your heart’ as working for the Lord* (Col. 3:23). This is an instruction to the slaves in a work context. Thus, we are expected to work with all our hearts as we are expected to love the Lord with all our hearts.

Let me now discuss the concept behind the Hebrew word *Avodah*. The word ‘*Avodah*’ is used in the Bible to describe both ‘Work’ (common labor) and ‘Worship’ (serving God, building the Tabernacle or sacrifice offered at the temple in Jerusalem). According to Patrick Lai, the word occurs hundred and forty-five times in the Bible and its verb form, ‘*avod*’ occurs two hundred and eighty-nine times (Jos. 24:14; Exo. 5:18). When God calls Moses to lead his people out of Egypt, God gives Moses this promise: *When you have brought the people out of Egypt, you will ‘worship’ [avad] God on this mountain* (Exo. 3:12). In the Ten commandments we also see that *six days you shall ‘labor’ [avad], but on the seventh day you shall rest* (Exo. 34:21). Thus, work and worship are closely connected. God gives equal significance to both, and we could say that work is an act of worship.

Work is an act of worship if it is done with the following principles as we see in Col. 3:22-24. First, we should have sincerity of heart and reverence for the Lord. It is significant to have integrity and commitment to work. We should not be

insincere in our work. Similarly, fear of the Lord is important in our work. Second, both worship and work must be done with all our hearts. God will not accept half-hearted worship, and neither will he accept half-hearted work. Third, we should work as if we are working for the Lord. If we are working for our selfish ambition or to satisfy our pride and if we are workaholics where our work has become an idol, it is not worship. Work is worship if we are working for the Lord. God does not judge us based on results but on motives. Fourth, through our work, we need to be serving the Lord Christ. It is good to reflect on whom we are serving. Our boss? Our ego? Our ambition? Work is an act of worship when it is offered as a service to God.

Our approach to work

Having understood the Biblical perspective of work, let me now portray what should be our approach to work. I would like to discuss two things here: work as a vocation and workplace as a mission place. There are four ways we generally approach our work. First, as a Job, something for me to earn my living; second, an occupation, something for me to engage myself; third, as a career, a place where I could improve my skills; and fourth, a vocation, calling, an avenue where I could engage with conviction and devotion.

When we are called, everything we are, do, and have, is invested with a special devotion, dynamism, and direction lived out as a response to God's summons and service. We may be confronted with a question here, is work really a calling? In Exo. 35:30-36:1, we see that Bezalel and Oholiab were chosen or called (v. 30) and they were filled with the Spirit of God, with skill ability, and knowledge. They were not priests or prophets, but craftsmen. They were 'called' for that work. Similarly, in Acts 6:1-6, we see that seven men full of Spirit and wisdom were 'chosen' to serve on the tables. The work assigned to them was the distribution of food.

Hence, each work has a calling, and it has its own significance. In the creation, God entrusted the stewardship of the entire universe in the hands of human beings. It is our responsibility to take care of it as God's ambassadors. If we have to take care of the entire universe, we need to take care of each and every aspect of it. If we do not handle it, we are failing in our responsibility.

Be it economic challenges of the nation, technological advancements to make the human's and other living creations' life on earth comfortable, taking care of the health of the created beings through medical science, enlightening the hearts and minds of the pupil through education, drafting right policies and legislation to govern the nation, ensuring proper administration of law and order or social wellbeing, all the areas need to be taken care. Thus, whatever profession we are engaged with—a teacher, doctor, engineer, administrator, politician, or banker—it has significance to God. God has a purpose behind each work. Similarly, the subjects our children study in school or college have significance to the Lord. As Christians, it is our responsibility to understand the purpose behind our work and get involved in public life. We should be channels of God's blessings to the entire universe.

Let me here now emphasize that a workplace is a mission place. The great commission as we see in Matthew 28:18-20 mandates us to make disciples of all nations. It is good to have a reflection on how it can happen in our country, in our generation. According to the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) statistics, the proportion of the working-age (15-64 age) population in India is 67.5 percent in the year 2021. It indicates that more than 2/3rd of the people of the country are working or actively preparing for work. It is further expected to increase.

We found that most part of an individual's life is spent in the workplace and the majority of Indians belong to the working-

age population. If so, the most effective mission approach to witness among them should be through marketplace ministry. This would happen when Christians in the workplace expand their mission understanding from not just reaching out to people in cross-cultural situations to witnessing to people in our circle of influence in the workplace. In this case, an IT professional employed in a company becomes a missionary in their own place of work.

If God is calling one to the ministry in the church, ministry in a remote village, or ministry with an NGO, they should follow that. However, if their calling is to be a workplace minister, one should follow that. It all depends on what is our call and what is our vocation. The vocation of being a teacher or engineer is as important as the vocation of being a pastor or evangelist in the church. We need to understand God's call on us and engage in our vocation with all our hearts.

As we grow in our missionary vision, we could start thinking more strategically. We could consider which area is needier. Can I move to another 'mission field' meaning another company, another office where the Christian presence is relatively less? For students, when we think of higher education can we consider choosing a college where the Christian presence is lower? Can parents consider taking admission for their child in such a college intentionally, so that he or she could witness there?

While considering workplace as a mission place, one may also be confronted with a dilemma whether they should focus on the 'ministry' at the cost of their daily work. My suggestion to them is that they should not do so. The mandate to work and worship the Lord came even before the fall of humans. Thus, the redemption mandate should not nullify the creation mandate. Our excellence in work should speak for us. When people see the difference in us, they may ask us about the difference in us. When we take a stand for God, we would get great opportunities

to witness Christ. For example, when confronted with a question of paying bribes, if we take a stand not to do so, based on Biblical values, others may not initially like it. But when they face critical issues in their life, they will come to us to pray for them. That will be an opportunity to share about the Christ in us with them.

In conclusion, let me assert that God is interested in our total being. There should not be any compartments in our life. For God, our Monday-Friday life is as important as our life on Sunday. God created us to work, and our work should be a worship to the Lord, a sweet aroma that is acceptable to God. Let us make a conscious effort to avoid any Monday blues. Let us wake up on Monday morning and say, 'Hey it's a Monday.' The workplaces have been designed by God to worship him. When we do that, we will be able to influence our colleagues in a positive way and could effectively witness among them. Through that, we would fulfill the Great Commission, and God's name would be glorified.

8

NO MORE SLAVES BUT FRIENDS

A REFLECTION BASED ON JOHN 15:12-17

Baby Rani*

Prayer

Dear God, we acknowledge that your word is a lamp to our feet and a light to our path. We ask that you open our hearts and minds to receive your message and comprehend the truth you want to disclose. Amen.

Introduction

Friends are important people in both good and bad times; they give us new strength, push us on, and inspire us with their acts. Friendship is normally viewed as a uniquely personal relationship that is based on a mutual concern for each other's welfare. Further, it demands some level of closeness and sincerity. Friendship unites all people from all backgrounds and times. Friends and friendship play the most important roles in every culture and situation. Without friends, life becomes dull, frail, and constrained. With friends, life is expanded and enriched. Friendship facilitates sharing of successes and joys. Even though the languages used or the ideas that constitute, friendship differs in each person's life. Race, gender, culture, caste, class and language are not barriers to friendship. The reading from John 15:12-17 today emphasizes the value of friendship. For our brief contemplation, I have concentrated on verse 15. I do not call you servants any longer, because the servant does not know what

* Dr. Baby Rani is Associate Professor and Chairperson in the Department of Women's Studies, The United Theological College, Bengaluru, India.

the master is doing, but I have called you friends because I have made known to you everything that I have heard from my father.

The Gospel of John 15 is the second part of the farewell discourse, and part one is recorded in John 13:31–14:31. Of course, scholars have different opinions on this topic. John 15:1–8 and 9–16 speak of remaining. The first is remaining in the vine (Jesus) and the second is remaining in Jesus' love. However, the selected pericope starts with love one another and ends with the same note or command of saying love one another. It is fascinating to note that NT scholars explain that in all the places where Jesus gives this command. He never uses the imperative form of the verb. Instead, Jesus says that he is giving them a command and then explains that the command is using a subjunctive. There by, the later statement, which follows that Jesus is not talking to slaves but to friends (15:15). In other words, it is not an option or a choice, but it is compulsory and also essential to have friendship with Jesus. Jesus the true friend explains to his disciples about love and teaches them how to love one another faithfully. Jesus explains and demonstrates the qualities of a true friend and expresses genuine love for God. There are many ways we can express or show God's genuine love to the people. It is very simple: accept the 'other' and demonstrate the same through action.

The yearning/desire of a true friend

It is easy to think we can become friends with God by doing a lot of work for God. Oswald Chambers, in his classic devotional, *My Utmost for His Highest*, says, "The most important aspect of Christianity is not the work we do, but the relationship we maintain (with God) and the surrounding influence and qualities produced by that relationship. That is all God asks us to give our attention to, and it is the one thing that is continually under attack. Accepting and understanding others' opinions, beliefs, and perspectives is the basis for friendship that normally occurs

with friendships in the world. Nevertheless, sincere friends continue to form bonds with people despite their flaws. They genuinely love them and find some aspects to be wonderful and sincere. I believe it is rare to see this kind of friendship. Because of this, we may affirm that only Jesus is our true friend. Additionally, we can notice that the word “love” is used in the chapter in the present tense, indicating that this is how disciples are expected to live. They are to love everyone, at all times. The Greek word used to express the idea of love here is the familiar term *agape*, the love that follows God’s example of loving in spite of, not because of. The inference is that, this love should continue until each disciple’s own time of departure, which means the father’s love and son’s love are expressed, an everlasting love that does not count the cost.

Peace with God is attained through reconciliation, mending the rift caused by our sin. Here is where friendship with God must start. It is right that we should direct our lives according to the commandment of Christ. So, we must understand what God’s will is. The will of Jesus Christ is to fulfill God’s purposes on earth through the command to love others. In Matthew 7:21, Jesus says, “Not everyone who says to me, ‘Lord, Lord,’ will enter the kingdom of heaven, but only the one who does the will of my Father who is in heaven.” Here, “the will of God” clearly refers to obedience to God’s revealed will for how we should live and love one another. Many times, we stray from this commandment and we follow our own limitations. Therefore, he now repeats what he had said before; that above all He wishes believers to cultivate mutual love among them. Love and reverence for God certainly come first in order, but, as the genuine proof of it is love toward our neighbors and God dwell specially on this point.

The expectation of a true friend

A true friend is always expecting something great and good, and s/he rejoices over it. Jesus expressed and demonstrated

true love and friendship through action by speaking and voicing for helpless and needy people. This we observe all through the gospels, where Jesus speaks on behalf of the poor and needy (Luke 6:9). Then Jesus said to them, "I ask you, is it lawful to do good or to do harm on the Sabbath, to save life or to destroy it?" After looking around at all of them, he said to him, "Stretch out your hand." He did so, and his hand was restored. In the same way we can see even in Luke 14:1-6 Jesus confronted with a leader of the Pharisees and lawyers, by questioning "Is it lawful to cure people on the Sabbath, or not?" But they were silent. So, Jesus took him and healed and then he said to them, "If one of you has a child or an ox that has fallen into a well, will you not immediately pull it out on a Sabbath day?" There are many examples like this in all the gospels, where Jesus speaks for the helpless and needy. So, Jesus became a true friend, expressed true love, and fulfilled the expectations of God, the parent. Through works and deeds Jesus epitomized the true love. So, Jesus points out to his disciples that the highest level of love for a friend is to be prepared to die for the sake of that friend. This word in Greek means 'doing in the place of another,' Jesus insists that 'this kind of love,' you are to have for each other.

Lay aside all selfish ambitions and ill-will of any kind but wish each other well, and work for what is best for one another. Here is one such example what happened thirty years ago and finally judgment came just two days before. This incident happened in one of the villages in Tamil Nadu. The Madras High Court on Friday, September 29, upheld the convictions of over 200 government officials from the forest, police and revenue departments of Tamil Nadu for the atrocities committed on the residents of Vachathi tribal village in Dharmapuri district in 1992, including cruelty, rape and ransacking village properties. They assaulted women, damaged village properties and killed their cattle. Eighteen women were raped and tortured and many men were beaten up. More than hundred women and children were

taken into custody and jailed for months under fake charges. It was only in June 2011, almost twenty years after the incident, that the designated trial court sentenced all the 215 surviving persons of the 269 accused in the case, including 126 forest personnel, 84 police personnel and five revenue personnel, and four Indian Forest Service (IFS) officers as well. The rest of the accused passed away during the course of the investigation. The jail terms for the various offences they were convicted under ranged from one year to 10 years. The point here is that 30 years after these innocent, powerless, underprivileged and deprived people got justice. This is in view of the fact that, men and women raised their voices against unjust structures of government. Justice Velmurugan directed the Tamil Nadu state government to pay compensation of Rs. 10 lakhs to each victim and give them suitable employment. He also called for stringent action against the then district collector, district forest official and superintendent of police for having failed to take action despite complaints regarding the atrocities.

Pleasing the desires of a true friend through service

Service for me is not related to our *Bhakti*, for many *Bhakti* is only devotion to God and nothing to do with service or helping the other. Our prayers, meditations, and Bible readings should be practiced through service. Love through service is something moving beyond our limitations and reservations. A scholar David Rensberger calls “love” would mean not only affection and a general kindness but standing with others in the community against betrayal by outsiders and participating actively in creating the new communal bonds that must take the place of the lost synagogue fellowship. He also states sacrificing of life is not an abstract model of general self-sacrifice then, but an expression of commitment that flows directly from the relationship. The word of God clearly says in the first letter of John 2:7-11: Beloved, I am writing to you no new commandment, but an old commandment that you have had from the beginning;

the old commandment is the word that you have heard. Yet I am writing you a new commandment that is true in him and in you, because the darkness is passing away and the true light is already shining.

Whoever says, "I am in the light," while hating a brother or sister, is still in the darkness. Many people follow the commandment of Jesus without understanding what it means actually, like a rich young man in the gospel narrative. In this juncture prophet Joel calls, rend your heart and not your garments (Joel 2:13). *A Chance to Die* is a vibrant portrayal of Amy Carmichael, an Irish novelist and missionary who lived in South India for fifty-three years without taking a break. She established the Dohnavur Fellowship, a shelter for underprivileged kids, and became known as "Amma" or "mother," there. For all who call themselves followers of Christ, Amy's life of obedience and gallantry endow an example. She sacrificed her life in devotion to her Master despite her aspirations, dreams, and flaws.

Conclusion

Ministry is something that you are doing than talking. Ministry is not only proclaiming the word of God but also challenging the structures. Friendship is defined by Jesus' love. To be a friend of Jesus is to love Jesus and be loved by him. The community commissioned by Jesus can do the works of love. Remain in me and remain in love re-state the purpose of Jesus' words. How one can imitate God's love? It is only possible by following the footsteps of our savior Jesus Christ. The word of God revealed to men and women of all periods of time. Some ignore and some take advantage of God's grace and they go their own way, and some afraid to face the challenges. But the love of God demands to bear fruits. Strive and try to imitators of Jesus' love. Remain in Jesus and bear fruits in fulfilling the purpose of God through your service by loving one another where we become true friends of Jesus Christ the Savior. May God Bless you all.

QUIET DAY MESSAGES IN 2023

Bethel Krupa Victor*

Message-One: True faithfulness

Text: Matthew 5:17-20

In simple terms, to be responsible or to hold a responsibility means to be faithful to the task entrusted with or what is given. All of us are responsible persons/individuals in our own terms and functions. To be responsible is to be watchful, to protect. Responsible freedom in the context of religion is often understood as an activity of safeguarding and defending one's faith. There can be two different categories of being faithful: first, to be faithful to what is entrusted with and it requires making effort to safeguard; and second, being faithful with regard to the possibilities hidden in time. Often the second category is not of a priority or less real for most people. The latter is, however, an innate aspect of faithfulness. With this in view, as we meditate upon the theme 'Responsible Freedom,' the annual theme of reflection, I would like to explore and understand being faithful in the following manner: Session-one, what is true Faithfulness; Session-two, models of true faithfulness; and Session-3, way to exercise true Faithfulness.

Faith is the evidence of things 'not seen.' The same has to be true as Jesus said, the kingdom of God is a 'hidden treasure' (Matthew 13:44). The kingdom is hidden not only in space but also in time. Such a faithfulness is accountable for what we receive.

* Rev. Dr. Bethel Krupa Victor is Presbyter of CSI St. John's Pastorate, Kazipet, Karimnagar Diocese.

This understanding is a limited outlook because it overlooks the fact that what is given includes in addition to what is materially visible today, such as talents, skills, foresight, freedom of choice, a spirit of enterprise and health and all of which comprise the bridge between present possession and future possibilities. Therefore, it is important to perceive what is given as the steppingstone to what can be. In other words, it implies to be open to the new possibilities available across. We need to remind ourselves that life is a domain of growth, not of stagnation. Theoretically we are conditioned to think and presume that being faithful is to be protective in the context. Often, we tend to focus on this at the cost of neglecting or ignoring the other possibilities.

Today a new trend is on. We see the promotion of a poisonous pedagogy which is rooted in hatred and violence. The agenda of VHP, RSS, Bajrang Dal and its allies is to establish Hindu regime and we are aware of its consequences. What is the root cause for Manipur issue? We do not have to discuss about the communal violence in states like Gujarat and other parts of the country. These are all part of fulfilling the agenda of the regime and promoting fundamental and fanatic ideology that negates life, peace and harmony. The root cause of such a dangerous ideology is the ideal of ownership—it is a tendency to think that a specific group/religion is responsible and has the right to protect and preserve the whole truth and it needs to be safeguarded by any means. It leads to violation and violence as the ownership 'mentality' gains ascendancy on us. Protectionism is inherent in ownership; wealth is incomplete without walls. It is important to discern the truth that safeguarding religion, its ideologies and practices are not marks of authentic faithfulness. As a counter to it, Jesus in the Sermon on the Mount presents a radically different agenda. It does not present the political or material blessings of Messianic reign but rather it expresses the spiritual implications that Christian living or living in Christ.

In Matthew 5:14-16, Jesus gives both a great compliment and a great responsibility. Compliment is that we are the light and we are the salt. It reminds us that the life marked by the beatitudes is not to be lived in isolation. Often times we believe that those inner qualities can only be developed or displayed in isolation from the world but Jesus wants us to live them out before the world. We as Christians are not just light receivers but light-givers. Jesus claimed that title for himself in John 8:12 and 9:5. Jesus never challenged us to become salt or light but he says that you are or we are the light of the world and salt of the earth. These are Christian distinctions. In order to be effective, we must seek and display these distinctive characters as we are responsible disciples. The objective of our shining is not that others may see how good we are, but they may see grace in us, in other words, God in us. In Matthew 5:17-18, Jesus was not opposing what God gave to Israel and his job was not to destroy the law or the word of God; but his duty was to free it from being interpreted wrongly. Jesus fulfils the law and the prophets and they point to him and he is their fulfilment.

In Romans 10:4 Paul says, for Christ is the end of the law there may be righteousness for everyone who believes. This text clearly shows us, the law sends us to Jesus, the saviour to be redeemed and justified pointing to our inability to please God in ourselves. In going to Jesus, we are again sent back to the law to learn the heart of God for our conduct and sanctification. It is in this sense, Jesus moves forward to redefine the authentic faithfulness and says verse 20 unless your righteousness exceeds that of the scribes and Pharisees you will never inherit the kingdom of heaven. The Pharisees were so scrupulous in their keeping of the law that they would even tithe from small spices obtained from their herb gardens. (Matt. 23:23). In this verse, Jesus is showing them the outcome of ownership mentality of the Pharisees which is most unfortunate and destructive. They drove a wedge between two models of faithfulness.

The Pharisees were obsessed with the righteousness of the law and were blind to the righteousness in Christ. Their religious life and ceremonial rituals are a proof for their earnestness in pursuing their religious agenda, which they mistook as for faithfulness focusing on what is not essential, mere zeal does not amount to faithfulness. The characteristic feature of the righteousness of the Pharisees was like Acts 23:6 that says it is divisive; in 26:5, self-propagation; in Phil 3:5, righteous under the law and persecutor of the church. We need to remind ourselves that, though the righteousness of Pharisees and scribes was impressive to human observation, it could not prevail before God (Isa. 64:6). Therefore, it is evident that we are not made righteous by keeping of the law and the law has no ability to make us righteous.

Faithfulness as Jesus points out is 'fulfilment.' The goal of being faithful in Christian life is not 'protection' of faith but fulfilment of the message of the Gospel. Therefore, Jesus says, think not that I have come to abolish the law and prophets but I have come to fulfil them. Jesus says in v. 20 for I tell you, unless your righteousness exceeds that of scribes and Pharisees, you will never enter the kingdom of God. It points out a crucially fundamental distinction and it is indeed a hallmark of Christian faithfulness and true discipleship. Virtually the sole agenda of religion for the Pharisees was to protect and preserve the Law and the prophets. This very outlook prevented their fulfilment of the law. Thus, religious faithfulness of Pharisees turns out to be their spiritual unfaithfulness because their zealous faithfulness to religion and its observances amounted to their hostile unfaithfulness to God. Whenever the scope of faithfulness is reduced to fanatical and exclusive obsession with the status quo, it becomes an anti-value, a sort of unfaithfulness to the logic of life and the unfolding purposes of God.

Then how can we exceed their righteousness, the righteousness of Pharisees and the scribes? Is it possible? Yes, it is possible. Phil. 3:6-9 provides the possibility for us to exceed in kind not degree. Paul describes two types of righteousness in these verses, Righteousness in the law which is of one's own and righteousness in Christ which is gained through faith in Jesus Christ. Is it not a joyful thing to remind ourselves that we are made righteous by faith in Christ and we need to strive to gain such righteousness.

As theologians we tend to think/assume that we are the custodians and we are defenders of God and Christian faith therefore we are anxious to speak, write and publish. My teacher Samson Prabhakar, former faculty at UTC used to say God does not a human defender, God knows how to defend himself/herself. You do not have to worry and we are not called for that, but most of our ministries reflect that attitude.

Jesus says, unless your righteousness exceeds that of the Pharisees. How is it possible? It is possible only in seeking God, knowing God intimately. Seeking involves two things: first, recognizing the fullness of what is given in the present; and second, discovering the possibilities hidden in time. Yes, true faithfulness is being faithful to new possibilities that are hidden in time. This is not what we do in practice. That is why Jesus prescribes 'seeking' as a core spiritual duty (Matt. 6:33). Seek ye first the kingdom of God and its righteousness and all things shall be added unto you. It is in seeking kingdom's righteousness we are made to exceed the righteousness of Scribes and Pharisees.

Our righteousness is not of the law but by faith we are made righteous and it is possible only by seeking and faithfully emulating his goodness. Responsible freedom is not only being responsible for what is given but it is also important to be open and vigilant for new possibilities that can make us to understand who God is and what God desires of us. It is not in protecting the law but by unconditional obedience to the

word of God is authentic faithfulness. May the Good Lord help us as we continue to strive to be responsible community in the contemporary context.

Message-Two: Models of true faithfulness

Text: Mathew 25:14-30

We have tried to understand what true/authentic faithfulness is and discovered that seeking God's righteousness is true righteousness. We are no defenders of God but we are followers of Christ the servant Lord. Responsible freedom is not only being responsible for what is given but it is also important to be open and vigilant for new possibilities that can make us to understand/discern who God is and what God desires of us. It is not in protecting of the law but in unconditional obedience to the word of God we are authentically made faithful. Here, I would like to draw our attention to discover authentic models of faithfulness.

A man was travelling to a far country and called his servants and gave them his goods. This was not a strange idea in the ancient world. Where servant-slaves were often given great responsibility which was the safest and smartest thing a person could do with his money. A best thing he could do in his absence was dividing the asset among carefully selected slaves and leave them to do their best with it. The intension of Jesus' parable here is to answer the question of 'preparedness' or 'readiness.' So, the master in the text gave five talents to one, to another two, and to another one. A talent was not ability but a unit of money with worth. The talent was not coin, it was a weight therefore its value definitely depended on whether the coinage involve was copper, gold or silver. It is simply a sum of money. We need to see these talents as life resources such as time, money, abilities and authority.

Distribution of the money was not random but according to their abilities each one was given. In that capacity, one servant got only one talent. Yet we should see that this was not an insignificant amount; though some received more, everyone received something. It was the talent which each one suits his own state best. Each of them did something with it as they saw fit. Two of them traded with their talents and earned more. It shows their attitude towards the responsibility given to them or the assignment. They did not delay. We are not told how they traded with it. The point is that they used what they had and gained more by using. We can say many things about the work of the first two servants. They did their work promptly, they did their work with perseverance, and they did their work with success. They were ready to give an account to their master.

Contrary to it, he who had received one went and dug it in the ground. The third servant did nothing with that money. He took some care that it would not be lost, but he did nothing positively with his master's money until the master returned. The long delay might have tempted him to think that he would never give an account for it. After a long time, the lord of those servants came and took account. The first two servants were rewarded saying you have been faithful over a few things; I will make you rulers over many things. Even though one was given 5 talents and the other was given 2 talents, the reward was the same for both the servants. The master said, well done, good and faithful servant; it shows that the master looked for goodness and faithfulness in his servants. Enter into the joy of your lord. This has echo of heaven in it—it is the portion of the master shared with his faithful servants. Often times, we tend to neglect the enormous number of possibilities that are available for our understanding of the theme faithfulness. These new possibilities would open up new avenues to experience God's love. In this passage, responsible freedom is understood in terms of being faithful to the task given.

Using the words of Jesus in the parable of the talents we may say that true faithfulness involves being 'good and faithful' and it was the response or declaration of the master on taking of the account (Matt. 25:21). The Master in the text points out to a duty to ensure that his servant's faithfulness is indeed 'good.' This implies that there could be 'bad' faithfulness too. Bad faithfulness is not better than unfaithfulness. We become unfaithful to God because of our faithfulness to something else or if only we do not endeavour to be 'good and faithful servants.'

The person whom one talent was given proved himself to be 'wicked' rather than 'good' even though he was careful enough to preserve whatever was entrusted to him. I often feel uneasy about the excessive harshness meted out to this servant because he was, after all faithful enough to keep it safely and preserve as you and I do with whatever was given or entrusted to. He did not squander it and ask the master to forget and forgive. I feel he presents our idea of faithfulness. Perhaps he has taken an extra effort to be better than us by hiding it in the ground. When the account was settled, he was dare enough to say what he did with the talent given to him. Here is what you have entrusted to me, take it. However, the important point that the parable makes is that this is not faithfulness.

These days I was travelling frequently; I often see cloak room both in bus station and in train station. As I read the response of the one talent servant, I was reminded of the task of a cloak room which delivers up whatever has been deposited there. Similarly, the one talent servant clearly indicates the cloakroom model of faithfulness to the master. Whatever is given, he is able to return the same even after a long time. This is not a true faithfulness and it is not sufficient. Christian faithfulness is beyond that, or our faithfulness to God should exceed these human confinements. From the perspective of our 'Faithfulness we cannot really find fault in the one-talent servant. He was not culpable in terms of

the cloakroom model of faithfulness. Yet one talent servant was judged, condemned and punished. In contrast, the first two servants saw the talents received as the medium for seeking further and fuller possibilities. They saw the future in the present, which made dynamism possible. This made them good and faithful servants, which is similar to upper-room model as a counterpart to the cloak room model.

In the upper-room, Jesus breaks his body and gives it away to be multiplied over the centuries. It is a sacrament which is an embodiment of true faithfulness. A sacrament is meant to bring out the new possibilities hidden in every human being, both now and forever. It is in this potential nature of proactive and redemptive implications the Lord's Supper becomes an agency of transformation in the contemporary context. Jesus envisioned the fellowship meal as a sacrament of true faithfulness, to God and to human beings. It is a hand of benediction stretched over future possibilities; hence, it is an invitation to fullness of life. It is a revelation of sacrificial and self-emptying love for creation.

Then how are we to understand what it means to be good with respect to faithfulness? To be good and faithful is to seek the fullness of the given things. God alone embodies the fullness of everything in all states and possibilities. God reveals himself that we must seek the goodness of God. Seeking is to find and what we find includes among other things the truth about whether or not we have attained fullness with respect to a given situation or a person. Seeking fullness implies a state of spiritual responsiveness described by Jesus with the word 'watch and pray.' Readiness is being on the work of the Lord. We need to ask what we have done with our knowledge, time, money and abilities. True faithfulness is sacramental and it is embodiment of Christ's goodness in all aspects of our life. May the good Lord lead us and help us to seek and attain the fullness in Christ who is good and a source of fullness.

Message-Three: The way to true faithfulness

Text: Mathew 2:1-18

During message-one, we have tried to understand the true/authentic faithfulness and discovered that seeking God's Righteousness is true righteousness. We are no defenders of God but we are followers of Christ the servant Lord. Responsible freedom is not only being responsible for what is given but it is also important to be open and vigilant for new possibilities that can make us to understand/discern who God is and what God desires of us. It is not in protecting of the law but in unconditional obedience to the word of God we are authentically made faithful. Message-two focused on true models of faithfulness based on the parable of talents. The first two servants saw the talents received as the medium for seeking further and fuller possibilities. They saw the future in the present, which made dynamism possible. This made them good and faithful servants, which is similar to upper-room model as a counterpart to the cloak room model. To be good and faithful is to seek the fullness of the given things. God alone embodies the fullness of everything in all states and possibilities and we need to find that fullness manifested in Christ. Our act of finding must lead us towards obtaining fullness in Christ. In the final message, I would like to draw our attention to the way of exercising true faithfulness.

The passage read to us describes the visit of wise men and great massacre of infants at the time of Jesus' birth. The text very clearly narrates the journey of the wise men and it gives additional insights into the question of true faithfulness. The wise men from the east saw a unique star, symbolizing the birth of an extraordinary person. They concluded that the star denoted the birth of the king of the Jews. It was their presumption that royal births were by nature extraordinary events. Second, they presumed that such a king would be born in a palace and not in a manger. Both of these are plausible assumptions but they are

not ultimate assumptions. Being captured by their presumptions they failed to identify possibilities hidden in place and time. They overlooked and failed to discern the truth. Seeking the kings that rise and fade away on the stage of history and seeking the king of kings and king of eternity are entirely different entities or enterprises. The wise men's faithfulness to the prevailing notions or assumptions proved to be unfaithfulness to the emerging possibilities.

Consequently, the event resulted in unthinkable atrocity, the massacre of thousands of children/infants. Mistaking faithfulness leads to dangerous consequences. The way to exercising true faithfulness involves rising above stereotypical assumptions. In order to exercise responsible freedom, one needs to come out of prejudices and stereotypes that continue to block them from exercising absolute faithfulness to the Gospel.

Therefore, after their visit to Jesus in the manger, they were directed to go home by another way. We must understand that, as long as we insist on sticking to our assumptions and beaten path, we shall miss the means to true faithfulness. Unthinking and fanatical adherence to orthodoxy would lead us to greater unfaithfulness and make us to be irresponsible and abuse the freedom that we have at our disposal. It is a dangerous state of being conditioned, not able to think out of the box or creatively engage with the facts. It also points to unwillingness to come out of the comfort zones to think and respond or to be creatively be an alternative way. The message that the angel of the Lord gave to the wise men that there is another way is quintessential divine guidance. Responsible freedom should lead us to discern the other way to exercise our faithfulness to God. Jesus Christ was able to see his life and ministry as an alternative to the conventional understanding of it. The Nazareth manifesto (Luke 4:16-19) very clearly demonstrates it. Jesus went about doing good things with a knowledge about the reward—the cross and

the crucifixion. To be an alternative means to be willing to pay a price.

To be able to measure up to the demands of true faithfulness, it is important for us to rise above the seductions of the present. We see same attitude among the women who came to the place where Jesus was buried. They went to the tomb early in the morning to find Jesus who is dead and buried, i.e., lifeless body to be embalmed to avoid decaying (Matt. 28:1-10). In the resurrection narratives of Mark 16, the women were saying to one another who will roll away the stone for us? In Luke 24:5, the angels ask, why do you look for the living among the dead? He is not here, he has risen. Remember what he told you, while he was still in Galilee (Mark 16:7). But go and tell his disciples that he is going ahead of you to Galilee, there you will see him, just as he told you.

The Church today is yet to capture this dimension in its ministry in the contemporary context. Christ cannot be found in the structures or institutionalised churches; Christ continues to be manifested on the streets and ordinary places of Galilee because that is the destination of the resurrected Christ. It is our task to be able to identify Christ in our day-to-day life situations, not in ivory towers but on the margins. Unless we are able to find Christ on the margins, among the excluded and stigmatized, the most vulnerable of the society, we continue to deceive ourselves. Remember that there is another way to be responsible and exercise responsible freedom. As we partake in the Holy Eucharist, may our hearts and minds be opened to discern the other way, that is, not a church on the hill tower but a fellowship at the foot of the mountains and in the valleys. Amen.

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RESPONSIBLE FREEDOM: BEING SPIRITUAL AND SOCIABLE

A REFLECTION ON PROVERBS 3:1-12

Ravela Jeeva Kumar¹

We have celebrated the safe landing of lunar on the surface of the Moon. India achieves greater things in the realm of technological innovations and scientific evolutions. However, the social backwardness is still a challenge while scientific success we achieve and applaud though. The contexts of multi-faith society, the divisive politics, the unfavorable socio-economic conditions, violence and sexism, and uncontrollable entertainment in the media or on digital platforms, and the negativism towards Christian services and mission activities in the country escalate a search for spirituality and social responsibility of Christian faith in order to respond to those strands of the society. On the one hand, the multiple ministries of the church look promising, but ineffective deliberations of the church about the formation of faith communities in all realms of life is disturbing and unimpressive on the other hand. Multiple ministries such as healing ministry, church planting, mission and evangelism, leadership development programs end up as traditional tasks of the mission of the church.

At this juncture, as a theological community, what can we learn and disseminate for the good of individuals and faith community is crucial to reflect further. What are the ways and means that

1 Rev. Dr. Ravela Jeeva Kumar is Professor in the Old Testament at the United Theological College, Bangalore. This is the sermon preached in the Sunday Service at UTC Chapel on 27th September, 2023.

the scriptures inform us about the responsible religious living, spiritually strong and ethically transformed life? In the process of learning the word of God and growing in faith in Jesus Christ, our teacher, what is the spiritual essence and sociable patterns we can fetch from the word of God? Can we search for the significant elements that can contribute to formulate Christian behavior or Character formation in the context of deplorable religious conditions in our society? Let us turn to the scripture portion read to us for a reflection on spirituality and sociability.

Proverbs is an appropriate book to do a self-bible study or personal meditation for private learning or a group discussion on various pressing concerns that men/women face in their day-to-day religious and social life. One may educate and motivate oneself to develop proper understanding of life, economy, social behavior and character formation. Probably, it may not be a probable book to preach on a Sunday worship service. Nevertheless, I find it more pertinent to share a few thoughts from the book Proverbs as part of my sermon. I realize that a sermon or reflection from the book of Proverbs would be enlightening us, as we have been pondering upon the theme '*Responsible Freedom*' in this academic year.

The book of Proverbs with its copious thoughts on various issues related to piety, Torah and wise behavior of individual informs the rich spiritual elements which may uncover the themes of liberation and liberative spirituality for human communities. It also encourages one to navigate one's social life in the light of the social thoughts and responsibilities. Therefore, I have chosen the theme, *Responsible Freedom: Being Spiritual and Sociable*, based on the text Prov 3:1-12. The book predominantly aims at equipping the young adults, teaching them the rich resources of the wise sayings in the form of instructions, admonitions, guidelines, religious/spiritual duties and moral responsibilities in order to help them having a formation which is the expectation of a

family and community in the days of antiquity. Though its origin is said to be during the reign of Solomon, the book's constructive instructions to follow the law in different situations of life probe one to locate its final composition in the context of temple schools during the post-exilic period. This book is to teach social and spiritual duties to individuals and communities, emphasizing the moral teachings for a responsible social and religious life. Therefore, the final edited book gives an impression that it is the amalgamation of both religious as well as social teachings. Perhaps, one cannot negate the core of parental advises and the wise teachings in the book that strive to shape the individuals in the family and in the schools in the ancient times. As a covenantal community, the ancient Israel firmly believed that equipping youngsters and adults in their religious and social life is very much required.

As part of the prologue, chapter 3 emphasizes the profound instructions of the teacher that are fraught with admonitions and directions. It is all about a summary of right human behavior toward God (vv. 1-12) and toward other people (vv. 21-25).² Verses 13-21 help the faith community to realize the broader cosmic space in which these relationships need to be properly exercised. The entire chapter focuses on the spiritual admonitions which follow spiritual consequences already explained in chapter 2. The buzz phrases 'fear the Lord and knowledge of the Lord' run through the prologue (Chaps 1-9) to indicate the significance of spiritual formation alongside the social transformation one needs to attain. Instead of giving importance to self and relying on one's own individual insights, teacher calls his/her listeners to learn and practice the instructions. The main emphasis, probably, is on the spiritual formation, social relationships and

2 Raymond C. Van Leeuwen, "The Book of Proverbs" in *The New Interpreter's Bible: A Commentary in Twelve Volumes*, ed. Leander E Keck (Nashville: Abingdon Press, 1997), 47.

character building which are the core responsibilities of every member in the faith community.

Verses 1-12 talk about the admonitions that aim at preparing one to be a trustworthy person in society. To live a satisfied spiritual life in terms of having a right relationship with God and living a responsible social life with all enjoyments, the teacher in the book gives us a set of views to grow in life in a way that is acceptable to God. Interestingly, both spiritual and social aspects are intertwined and there is no much difference in growing spiritually and socially in the sight of God. It does not mean that one can live a social life according to the commandments and teachings of the Torah which may be the indication of a healthy spiritual growth in one's life. No, that is not the meaning here. But, having a right spiritual growth directs one to grow responsibly in one's social life. In other words, spiritual life is a privilege to enjoy and social life is a responsibility to continue the given status of privileged spiritual life. I would like to draw your attention to understand these two aspects of life in the light of the teachings of proverbs. Based on Proverbs 3:1-12, first, let me share with you what is 'being spiritual' in the faith community and what is 'being sociable' in a worldly life.

Being Spiritual

In chapter 3:1-12 the main call is to trust, fear and honor God in all situations of life. It is the core of spirituality that the book extols. It begins with a call to learn and keep the teachings and commandments. The form of admonition leads the readers to learn them byheart and not to forget those emphatic words. The phrases 'do not forget' and 'keep the commandments in heart' lead one to receive the promises about the rich, comfortable and joyful life that the teachings and commandments deliver. God is the source of life and having a joyous life means that God provides an abundant life (John 10:10). This is possible when

one lives according to the teachings and commandments of God (Deut. 6:1-6). After describing the promises embedded in the teachings and commandments, it is a call to trust in the Lord (v. 5), fear the Lord (v. 7) and honor the Lord (v. 9). After every instruction, there is a social implication of the relationship with God. In other words, how should one live a spiritual life in terms of maintaining a right relationship with God which demands one to be socially responsible in his/her social life. In the first place, we will reflect upon the tripartite formula trust, fear and honor which echoes the very aim and objective of one's religious life that eventually aims at making one being spiritual.

'*Trust in the Lord*' reverberates the idea 'fear the Lord' and it consequently leads the teacher to accentuate 'honor the Lord.' The word used for trust (*bathach*) also means 'feel safe' (Deut. 28:52; 2 Kings 18:20); 'be full of confidence' (Isa. 12:2); and 'unsuspecting' or 'undoubting' (Judg. 18:10). It has been used in the context of encouraging personal relationship with God. When we trust in God, we will have to rely upon God for all the directions in our life. It is not that one can trust God and live his/her life as s/he deems it. Rather it is to live life 'feeling safe' in the presence of God, and being confident of whatever the task ahead to discharge and undoubtedly moving in our life. V. 5b teaches the admonition that our trust should lead us to rely on God. The trust also leads us to improve our knowledge about God. We learn of God by acknowledging God in our ways. The word *acknowledge* explicitly has the idea of *knowledge* in it.

The phrase '*Fear the Lord*' is an eclectic phrase in the book of proverbs. There are many sayings and declarations based on this phrase that pushes the people of God to hold on to the 'relationship with God' as priority above the cultic practices or traditional rituals or offerings that one brings to the presence of God (temple). The word 'fear' (*yarah*) means 'submission and reverence.' 'Fear the Lord' reminds the very responsibility of the

inner spirit that has to maintain a firm relationship with God. There are multiple benefits one receives if s/he fears the Lord. Acknowledge God 'in all your ways' leads one to fear the Lord thereby one turns from evil way. The word 'way' (*derek*) refers to human conduct in the world in its diversity.³ One needs to be aware of the fact that his/her knowing God reflects his/her own knowledge of God. Thus, this idea is also related to the word 'trust in the Lord' and rely on the Lord in all the days of your life.

Honour the Lord is a third direction given to the people of God. The phrase 'honor the Lord' in v. 10 indicates the materials that we bring to the Lord. Offering the first fruits of all the production is symbolically the best way to dedicate ourselves to God. Sometimes with our own actions we may scorn God (Gen. 14:31; 19:17; 1 Sam. 2:29; Dan. 11:38) thereby we are prone to the judgment of God. Our use of world and wealth reveals our true commitments as people of God. It also shows the way we use and abuse the spiritual relationship with God in the world. If you honor God, you will be growing in a right relationship with God or if you are in right relationship with God, you will be certainly honoring God with your best life. This part of spiritual teachings culminates in the way one prepares to live in the delight one takes in the discipline of God (v. 12). If you are committed to honor the Lord, you are expected to be bold in receiving reproof of God. This idea pushes further that God reproves one whom God loves and cares.

Your honor to the Lord returns to you in a way of God's correcting measure of your life and leading you to be in perfect relationship with God. Unless you are in the process of receiving such corrective measures from God, you will not grow in a right relationship with God. All these views remind the people of God about their spiritual responsibilities. Trusting in the Lord, fear the Lord and honor the Lord are the pivotal to one's personal

³ Van Leeuwen, "The Book of Proverbs," 49.

spiritual entities that display one's condition of spirituality. Dear, beloved people of God, we are called to exercise, experience and enjoy a right relationship with God by trusting in the Lord, fear the Lord and honor the Lord.

Being Sociable

Let us turn to the notion-being sociable. Can we affirm that all the spiritual directions have social implications in our behavior? Yes, of course. Your social life shows the way you live your spiritual life. There is no inseparability between spiritual and social aspects of life. While explaining the spiritual consequences one receives out of the relationship with God, being sociable is also equally emphasized here. There are three views that I would like to share with you from this text: *First*, equipping oneself in social values like welfare of all (v. 2), kindness, justice and fidelity (v. 3); *second*, acting with responsibly in one's social behavior by growing beyond ego and envy, and departure from evil ways (vv. 5b-6); *third*, sharing with others whatever you have been blessed by the Lord in terms of knowledge, wealth and love (the experience of being loved by God) (vv. 9b-10). Let me quickly present these views of what I mean to be 'being sociable' in one's life.

First, as part of growing in one's spiritual life, one is promised to have a beautiful life (vv. 1-2). Such a condition of life encourages us that the life should be fraught with social values like 'receiving the view of welfare of all' (v. 2), and 'learning to be kind' and growing in the state of fidelity in one's relationship (v. 3). The words 'kindness' (*chesed*) and faithfulness (*emet*, which actually means 'truth') are the virtues of a person who maintains a firm relationship with God. In fact, kindness and truthfulness formulate ones' faithful and obedient life before God. The people of ancient Israel were questioned by the prophets many a times because they need these values in their social life (Isa. 1:20;

Amos 5:14; Micah 6:6-8). When you are in right relationship with God, you will be certainly maintaining the same 'rightness' with kind and truth in your social life which can be labelled as 'being sociable.'

Second, rising yourself beyond ego, envy and departure from evil ways (vv. 5b-6). When you trust God, with all your heart you become meek and modest. There is no place in you the inculcation of own insights that may contradict the word/ wisdom of God. By trusting in the Lord, you will learn the wisdom of God which is replete with peace, gentleness, full of mercy and yield good fruits without a trace of partiality and hypocrisy (Jam. 3:13-18). Jesus is the source of such a wise life (Jesus is concealed wisdom, Col. 2:2-3). Instead of envy it is gentleness, in the place of ego it is full of mercy, and there is righteous behavior replacing wickedness. The dangerous traits of relying on self-wisdom instead of wisdom of God, narrowing one's path instead of broadening it with the assistance of God's words, and turning not from evil instead of changing one's direction of life in the light of the words of God need to be taken care. The recurring word, 'let your heart keep my commandments and teachings' (v. 1), 'write them on the tablet of your heart' (v. 3b), and 'trust with all your heart' (v. 5a) remind us the significance of the function of 'heart' in one's life. Heart is the manifestation of mind-set. The way you behave in your social life is an indication of the way your heart guides you in your spiritual life. For Hebrews, heart (*leb*) is the inner person which equips the outer person. Therefore, growing beyond all those unsociable conditions of life is the responsibility of one's spiritual life which consequently makes one 'being sociable.'

Third, sharing with others whatever you have gathered or gathering from a fruitful spiritual life. The abundance we receive from God is to be shared with our fellow human beings. It may not mean material goods but it is sociable attitude, conversion of oneself into the process of being good and perfect, and relating

to the people who suffer from lacking the basic amenities in the life. God instructs God's people to seek the good of others, not themselves but 'human beings supplant this teaching with their own wisdom to gratify themselves.' The basic commandments that Jesus reiterates in many occasions when different people ask him what shall we do to attain 'eternal life' (Matt. 19:16-22; Mark 10:17-22; Luke 18:18-25), and how to worship God (John 4:20-24). Worship the Lord in truth and in spirit is equal to behave with your fellow beings in truth and good.

As we see the present world with full of unsociable activities, violence, and irreligious and irresponsible attitudes to one another, our 'responsible freedom' must come in force to establish the uniqueness of Christian faith, Christian witness and Christian ministry. In the world of insensitive behavior and sorrow filled life situations, we are called to inculcate a sense of responsible spirituality and a style of sociable living in order to invalidate the wisdom of the world which perpetuates ego, stubbornness, disharmony, violence in human life. As we continue to meditate upon the theme 'responsible freedom,' may the good Lord guard us with the spirit of truth and wisdom so that we can discern what is to be being spiritual and being sociable. May the Lord lead us towards such an achievement. God bless you all, Amen!

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HOLY COMMUNION: COMMEMORATION AND THE EXPERIENCE OF THE SALVIFIC EVENT

A REFLECTION ON MARK 14:22-25

Philip Philip*

The Church receives the Holy Eucharist as a gift from the Lord. It is the source and summit of the Christian life. In the celebration of the Holy Eucharist, the Church commemorates the salvific experience manifested in the life and ministry of Jesus Christ. Let us ponder upon the meaning of Holy Qurbana for being a relevant witness in our contemporary context.

Commemoration and experience of God's sacrificial love

God's being and doings always witness God's Love in its fullest sense. Holy communion signifies the life, death, resurrection and the return of Jesus Christ. Jesus is the bread of life broken and poured out for many (Mark 14:22-25). His sacrificial death was the fullest expression of God's love in an embodied manner. Thus, the Holy Qurbana is the commemoration and experience of God's sacrificial offering for the world. As Andrew J. Kirk states, "Love belongs to the very essence of the Godhead . . . Love is not speculative, but is defined, understood and grasped by the way God acts (1 John 4:9)." When we partake in the holy

* Rev. Philip Philip is an ordained minister of the Mar Thoma Church. He is currently pursuing his doctoral studies at UTC in the Department of Missiology.

communion, we are experiencing and embracing God's love in our being, becoming and belonging.

Commemoration and experience of God's act of reconciliation

Holy Eucharist calls us for a covenantal relationship with God. The old covenant with Israel was based on Law. But the new covenant is dependent on God's Love and Grace (Mark 14:24). Thus, the Holy Qurbana is the mark of God's reconciling Love (God's Grace) which offers us a right and 'just' relationship with God, fellow human beings and even with the entire creation. We appropriate God's salvation offered in the Holy Communion by repenting and transforming our sinful alienation from God and God's creation. Thus, by partaking in the Holy Communion, we profess that we are both the reconciled and reconciling community.

Expectation and experience of the reign of God

Holy Eucharist signifies the presence of God and our hope in the eternal kingdom/reign of God. This is mentioned in Mark 14:25: "Truly I tell you, I will never again drink of the fruit of the vine until that day when I drink it new in the kingdom of God." However, this hope does not summon us into an otherworldly passivity but rather invokes us to be active agents for the extension of God's reign, which is already inaugurated with the life and ministry of Jesus Christ. By partaking in the Holy Communion, the church envisions its entity as the sign and sacrament of the reign of God. This understanding challenges us to manifest the values of the reign of God as the visible expression of our meaningful participation in the Holy Communion.

A call for eucharistic living

Myra Blyth states, "The action of 'remembering' (anamnesis) to which Christ called us is not just a rehearsal of a past event,

but it is also a forward-looking event, involving re-collecting, re-presenting, and re-committing to receive the sacramental energy for living." The celebration of Holy Communion must not be limited to a ritualistic act; its meaning must permeate all aspects of our lives. We are called to be the witnesses of Christ by transfiguring into a living liturgy of the Holy Eucharist (i.e., "Do this in remembrance of me"). Our office, our workplace or our home ought to become an altar of witness where our soul and body will be offered as a living sacrifice, holy, and acceptable to God (Rom. 12:1). As Ivone Gebera reminds us, "We are the food and drink of one another. We are one another's body and blood. We are one another's salvation." In other words, Holy Communion invites us to witness God's salvific act by being poured out as libation (Phil. 2:17). Thus, it demands offering (Qurbana) of our being and belonging for the meaningful witness of the gospel.

Conclusion

Let us re-dedicate ourselves as channels of God's love and reconciliation. Let the celebration of the Holy Communion invoke and provoke us to perceive God's mission in our contemporary context and participate in it meaningfully.

12

THE ART OF THEOLOGICAL REAPPRAISAL

DEVELOPING A FAITH-BASED INTERPRETATION TO LIFE

John Jebaseelan*

Neuroscientist Kevin Ochsner experimented on how our perception of things affect the neuro-physiological reaction to events. He showed a picture of a woman crying in front of a church to volunteers who felt sad and exhibited neurological signs of stress. But when they were told that the picture was taken at the wedding, their negative perception changed to happiness along with the neurological signs of happiness. He established that the same picture can elicit different responses based on different perceptions, and the change in outlook contributed to radical transformation of mood. This is ‘Cognitive Reappraisal.’

‘Cognitive Reappraisal,’ according to psychologists and neuroscientists, is one of the lifehacks to live a happier and healthier life. Cognitive reappraisal, also known as perception control and emotion regulation, is consciously interpreting the events happening in our lives in a different way than normal which will result in more positive interpretation. This conscious effort, they say, is the key to happiness in life. They affirm that perception matters more than the external circumstances.

* Rev. John Jebaseelan is an ordained minister of Mumbai Regional Conference of Methodist Church in India. He was a former faculty member of Union Biblical Seminary, Pune, and at present pursuing his PhD at University of Durham, UK, researching on fourth century church father Gregory of Nazianzus.

A real-life example comes from the life of the science writer Winifred Gallagher, who was diagnosed with an advanced stage of cancer. Soon after this diagnosis, she decided to change the way she viewed her life with the disease. She said, “this disease wanted to monopolize my attention, but as much as possible, I would focus on my life instead.” She consciously focused on small pleasures of life instead of the life threatening disease. Eventually she found that the human brain constructs its worldview based on what we choose to ignore and what we choose to pay attention to. She chronicled her discoveries on this amazing fact in her book *Raft: Attention and the Focused Life*. At the end, she proclaimed “Who you are, what you think, feel and do, what you love—is the sum of what you focus on.”

We as Christian leaders can take a leaf out of ‘cognitive reappraisal’ as this will be an asset while facing and dealing with challenges in ministry. Burnouts and bitterness in relationships are common in the ministerial world. I believe that they can be eradicated if every minister learns the art of reappraisal. What we choose to focus on and what we choose to ignore as we serve God matters, as it determines if we serve Him cheerfully or out of compulsion. The heroes of the Bible interpreted the events of their lives in the light of their theology and faith. When they faced impossible situations, their understanding of God or their theology became the lens through which they look at everything. I call this as ‘theological reappraisal.’ In our ministerial walk, we need theological reappraisal from time to time.

Joseph’s brothers had caused him great anguish when they sold him as a slave. Years of hardship, deprivation and loneliness followed but now his brothers were at his mercy (Genesis 42). In the next two chapters, we see Joseph struggling to deal with his brothers as he could not immediately reveal his identity. The Bible does not say much about Joseph’s inner struggles, but it describes the way in which he tackled his dilemma with theological reappraisal.

In Chapter 45 when he reveals himself, he says to his brothers “. . . do not be distressed and do not be angry with yourselves for selling me here, because it was to save lives that God sent me ahead of you . . . But God sent me ahead of you to preserve for you a remnant on earth and to save your lives by a great deliverance” (Genesis 45:5-7). Joseph chose to *re-interpret* the bitter events of his life through the lens of God’s sovereignty. He believed that God knew everything ahead of time and that He had written the script of his life perfectly. Joseph had every right to be angry with his brothers, but his theological reappraisal made him understand the bigger plan of God. He consciously paid attention to God’s hand in the bitter events of his life, and chose to ignore the malicious actions of his brothers. Although history remains unchanged, his understanding of God’s sovereignty brought peace in the midst of chaos.

Another striking example of reappraising life theologically comes from the life of Job. Job lost all of his wealth and all of his children on the same day (Job 1:13-19). However, Job’s clear understanding of God’s sovereignty and human dependency on God for everything made him utter the words “Naked I came from my mother’s womb, and naked I will depart. The Lord gave and the Lord has taken away; may the name of the Lord be praised” (Job 1:21). Job’s understanding of God made him aware that God was the source of all his blessings and so when tragedy struck, he looked at the events of his life in a different way.

As servants of God, we too may face many challenges and oppositions—within and without. These challenges often take their toll on our physical and mental health. Even in the midst of oppositions when we consciously adopt a cheerful attitude, we stop viewing ministry as a series of conflicts which one needs to endure for Christ. When we face such scenarios, theological reappraisal is a great tool which can alter our perception of events and make them an opportunity for us to grow in God.

This reappraisal will not happen automatically. We need to deliberately practise this in our day to day life. If we believe that our faith and belief in God is powerful, we should use it to interpret the events of our lives. Our conscious effort to bring our theology into our perceptions of events will enrich our lives. Theological reappraisal does not also mean that we are ignoring the reality and choosing to bury our heads in the sand. It is instead facing the realities of life with our faith. Joseph's painful past and Job's devastating loss were irreplaceable and unforgettable. Theological reappraisal did not make them to deny the realities of these painful events, but made them to face these realities and helped them to react to these realities in a godly way. In simple terms, it is seeing the events of life with God's perspective, even though our human instinct may react otherwise to the external circumstances.

In any situations in life and ministry, let us commit to evaluate and re-evaluate our approaches to challenges based on our faith and theology. Let us remember the examples of Joseph and Job, who in midst of their extraordinary circumstances used their faith and theology to consciously rephrase the narration and focus on God. Theological reappraisal will not only help us to grow in faith but it will also lead us to a happier life. Here are some ways to practice theological reappraisal in our life and ministry:

- Look for what God is trying to do in specific situations;
- Trust in His providence and believe in His plan completely, even though the situation could be depressing;
- Try to stop focussing on the negatives of the situation and start focussing on the positive learnings that God is granting through the situation;
- Deliberately re-interpret the events and situations using your faith in God.

13

CARING AND ACCEPTING THE ELDERLY

REFLECTIONS BASED ON GEN 46:28-47:10; 1 TIMOTHY 5:1-10;

LUKE 2:25-38

Arnon Christian¹

This meditation centers around the theme of “caring and accepting the elderly,” a crucial topic that often goes unaddressed in church discussions. This theme holds immense importance due to our current societal context. Our world tends to disregard the elderly, widows, and widowers, mainly due to the prevailing materialistic attitudes. This detachment from the concerns of the elderly is becoming more pronounced. Many elderly parents suffer from neglect as their children fail to find time for them in our fast-paced lives, leading to feelings of loneliness. This isolation is exacerbated by the loss of a spouse, creating a deep sense of solitude. The widening generation gap between the elderly and the young further contributes to this disconnect. The elderly often feel undervalued and disrespected by the younger generation, while the younger generation may feel misunderstood by the elderly. This mutual misunderstanding exacerbates the challenges faced by both groups. This societal disregard for the elderly is starkly evident in the increasing number of crimes against them, as indicated by a 2021 report. In India, incidents of crimes against senior citizens rose significantly over the past five years, with 27,976 reported cases in 2019 alone. These figures are

¹ Arnon Christian is doing his Master of Theology Final Year in New Testament studies at The United Theological College, Bengaluru, India.

likely an underestimation, considering unreported cases. Given this backdrop, how should Christians approach the elderly? To formulate a perspective, we must examine God's view of the elderly, widows, and widowers. If God holds a specific outlook towards them, we should strive to adopt the same. Let's delve into understanding God's perspective on the elderly.

Allow me to pose a question: Why did God choose to exile the nation of Israel? The prevailing answer often centers around their disobedience to God's commandments or their transgressions against Him, which resulted in their exile. However, if we accept this answer, another question arises: What specific actions did the Israelites commit that prompted God to enact this punishment of exile? While it is commonly mentioned that they turned to the worship of other deities and neglected their devotion to Yahweh, or that they violated various laws including the Sabbath commandment, these explanations only capture a part of the picture. Is that the entirety of God's concern? I urge you to shift your focus to what God communicated through His prophets regarding the collective wrongdoings of the Israelites that ultimately led them into exile.

First, let us turn our Bibles to Zechariah 7:8-10: "Then the word of the Lord came to Zechariah, saying, This is what the Lord of armies has said: 'Dispense true justice and practice kindness and compassion each to his brother; and do not oppress the widow or the [a] orphan, the stranger or the poor; and do not devise evil in your hearts against one another.'" In these verses, we come across a compilation of actions that Yahweh expected the Israelites to undertake, but unfortunately, they neglected to fulfill these responsibilities. It's worth noting that within this list, God emphasizes the importance of caring for various vulnerable groups such as widows, orphans, foreigners dwelling in the land, and the economically disadvantaged. While the elderly might not be explicitly mentioned, they undoubtedly belong to the

category of individuals who are often marginalized by society or subjected to exploitation. Now hear what God says next in vv. 11-14: “‘But they refused to pay attention, and turned a stubborn shoulder and plugged their ears from hearing. They also made their hearts as hard as a diamond so that they could not hear the Law and the words which the Lord of armies had sent by His Spirit through the former prophets; therefore great wrath came from the Lord of armies. And just as He called and they would not listen, so they called and I would not listen,’ says the Lord of armies; ‘but I scattered them with a storm wind among all the nations whom they did not know. So the land was desolated behind them so that no one went back and forth, since they made the pleasant land desolate.’” Evidently, what becomes apparent is that God’s desire was for the Israelites to provide care for this particular segment of the society that frequently goes unnoticed and faces oppression. Regrettably, the nation of Israel fell short in fulfilling this obligation, which ultimately led to their exile as a consequence from God.

Let us look at one more passage, Jeremiah 7:3-7: “This is what the Lord of armies, the God of Israel says: ‘Amend your ways and your deeds, and I will let you live in this place. Do not trust in deceptive words, saying, This is the temple of the Lord, the temple of the Lord, the temple of the Lord. For if you truly amend your ways and your deeds, if you truly practice justice between a person and his neighbor, if you do not oppress the stranger, the orphan, or the widow, and do not shed innocent blood in this place, nor follow other gods to your own ruin, then I will let you live in this place, in the land that I gave to your fathers forever and ever.’” Once more, within this passage, we encounter a specific group of individuals whom God acknowledges as frequently marginalized and subjected to oppression. God’s directive is for these individuals to receive proper care and safeguarding. God goes on to assure that if the Israelites rectify their conduct, ensure

justice, and refrain from exploiting the vulnerable, they will be allowed to inhabit the land bestowed upon their forefathers.

These passages make it evident that the Israelites' exile was not solely caused by idolatry or disobedience to God's commands. Equally accountable was their inability to establish justice and prevent the mistreatment of the vulnerable. This underscores that, according to God's perspective, tending to the needs of the elderly, widows, widowers, the poor, and those lacking parental care holds significant importance. God's heightened attention to this group arises from society's typical disregard for their well-being.

When we read the scripture, we can see a constant positive attitude of God towards the elderly, the widows, and widowers. In Deut. 10-16-19 it says: "So circumcise your heart, and do not stiffen your neck any longer. For the Lord your God is the God of gods and the Lord of lords, the great, the mighty, and the awesome God, who does not show partiality, nor take a bribe. He executes justice for the orphan and the widow, and shows His love for the stranger by giving him food and clothing." In Psalms 146:19 it says: "So show your love for the stranger, for you were strangers in the land of Egypt. The LORD protects the strangers; He supports the fatherless and the widow, But He thwarts the way of the wicked." In Exodus 22:22-23 it says: "You shall not oppress any widow or orphan. If you oppress him at all, and if he does cry out to Me, I will assuredly hear his cry." All these passages unmistakably emphasize that God exhibits exceptional care for the elderly, widows, and widowers.

God not only responds to their pleas by ensuring justice but also utilizes them in ways that might not be immediately apparent. A remarkable illustration of this is found in the Gospel passage, Luke 2:25-35. The account introduces us to Simeon, a righteous and devout individual who ardently awaited the comfort of Israel. The Holy Spirit was with him, and God had

made a promise that he would not pass away before witnessing the appearance of God's chosen Messiah. This divine pledge was fulfilled when Simeon had the privilege of cradling Jesus in his arms. Imagine the significance of holding the Messiah in your own hands! Yet, God's plan went beyond this privilege; Simeon was also instrumental in highlighting a significant facet of the Gospel message. In v. 32, Simeon says about Jesus that he is "A light for revelation for the Gentiles, And the glory of Your people Israel." This encapsulates the essence of Jesus' mission. His purpose extended beyond the confines of Israel to encompass all of humanity. He emerged as a universal beacon of light, transcending national boundaries.

While Israel anticipated a Messiah with a national focus, God's intention was to shine light upon all nations. This pivotal and inclusive dimension of the Gospel is vividly exemplified through the narrative of Simeon. He even goes on to say: "Behold, this Child is appointed for the fall and rise of many in Israel, and as a sign to be opposed." This highlights that Jesus, within people's lives, can evoke diverse reactions—acting as both a stumbling block and a sign that generates opposition. As foretold, these responses lead to division, causing some to stumble while others rise. This prophetic foresight finds its realization in the Gospel accounts. Thus, we can discern that God not only grants Simeon the privilege of encountering Jesus but also employs him to unveil a crucial facet of the Gospel and anticipate the contentious reactions towards Christ. However, Simeon is not the sole recipient of this privilege. In verses 36-38, we encounter another elderly individual, Anna, a widow. These verses introduce us to Anna, a prophetess, who remained a widow for eighty-four years after just seven years of marriage. She devoted herself unwaveringly to the temple, dedicating her days and nights to fasting and prayer. Remarkably, Anna too bears witness to Jesus. Although the text does not explicitly mention her holding Jesus, it is plausible to assume she did so. Similar to Simeon's

experience, Anna's encounter with Jesus extends beyond mere privilege; God utilizes her as well. In verse 38, we learn that she spoke of Jesus to all those awaiting Jerusalem's redemption. Thus, God employed her to herald the presence of the long-awaited Messiah, effectively spreading the joyful news of Jesus Christ's birth.

In our Christmas festivities, the focus often centers on angels, shepherds, and the wise men. Our carols and songs frequently celebrate them, while figures like Simeon and Anna receive comparatively little attention. This disparity extends to art and sermons as well. However, it is crucial to recognize that Simeon and Anna play an essential role in the narrative of Jesus' birth. These two devout elders were uniquely favored by God, granted the privilege to behold the Messiah before their passing. Furthermore, they served as instruments in revealing a significant aspect of the Gospel's message and in spreading the joyful news of the Messiah's birth. Despite the relative silence surrounding them, Simeon and Anna hold a remarkable position within the birth narrative, exemplifying the profound honor bestowed upon them by God.

Dear friends, as we have observed, God holds a special regard for the elderly, widows, and widowers. Not only does God provide for their needs and heed their pleas, but He also ensures justice for them. The stories of Simeon and Anna illustrate how God employs them in unexpected yet meaningful ways. This perspective is quintessentially divine, and as followers of God, it is imperative that we adopt this same viewpoint and disposition. Consequently, it becomes our responsibility to offer care and acceptance to the elderly, both within our families and our congregations. The scriptural passages we have explored from the Old Testament and the epistles serve as exemplary illustrations of this ethos. In mirroring God's compassionate outlook, we embrace our duty to uphold and cherish the elderly within our communities.

The narratives of Genesis 46:28 to 47:10 serve as remarkable instances of the personal care that should be extended to the elderly, exemplified by Joseph's actions toward his father and family. The well-known account of Joseph includes his adversities, his rise to power, and his forgiveness toward his brothers. These aspects are often emphasized in sermons and discussions, particularly in youth gatherings, where Joseph is held up as an exemplar of virtue and resilience in the face of temptation. However, the significance of Joseph's care for his elderly father and family can sometimes be overshadowed. Amidst his trials, Joseph arranges for his father and family to join him in Egypt during a time of famine. His meticulous planning and attention to detail are evident as he ensures their comfort and livelihood. He makes strategic arrangements to settle them in Goshen, a region suited to their occupation as shepherds. Joseph demonstrates his diplomatic skills by informing Pharaoh about his family's arrival and their profession. By highlighting their animals, Joseph subtly indicates their intention of a permanent stay, effectively securing their position in Goshen. Notably, Joseph orchestrates his brothers' encounter with Pharaoh before introducing his father, a deliberate choice that safeguards his father's dignity. He anticipates Pharaoh's inquiries about their occupation and strategically positions his brothers to request favor, sparing his father from such a direct interaction. This narrative shed light on Joseph's thoughtful and attentive care for his elderly father and family, exemplifying the kind of consideration and respect that should be extended to the elderly within our own lives.

To the young individuals, I encourage you to draw inspiration from Joseph's remarkable example in caring for the elderly. While I am uncertain about the practices in this community, in the place I come from, a concerning trend prevails. Parents often work tirelessly to send their children abroad for better opportunities, yet unfortunately, they may not receive the same level of care in return. Even those living in the same city might neglect their duty

to care for their aging parents, leaving them to fend for themselves during their senior years. There are instances where parents find themselves alone when they need their children the most. Let Joseph's model be a guiding light for us. Let us ensure that we actively care for the elderly, providing them with a comfortable living environment and meeting their needs. If feasible, consider bringing them closer to us so that we can be physically present to support them. Spend quality time with them, allowing them to experience the warmth of companionship and reassuring them that they are not alone. It is our responsibility to honor and care for the elderly just as Joseph did, fostering an environment of respect, love, and support.

We have examined a personal illustration of caring for the elderly, and now, in the epistle reading, we encounter a collective example of the church's responsibility toward the elderly, widows, and widowers. In 1 Timothy 5:1-10, Paul offers guidance to Timothy, advising him not to reprimand older individuals but to treat them with the respect due to parents. He then proceeds to discuss the care of widows. Of particular note is verse 9, which references a list. Some scholars suggest this was a support list, containing the names of women lacking family assistance and thus in need of provision. Others contend it was a list of widows eligible for specific church service. While I would not delve into the exact nature of the list, the mere mention of it underscores the collective obligation of the church toward the elderly. As a unified body, we are tasked with providing for those among us who require assistance and also with engaging them in service within the church, much like God employed Simeon and Anna. Today, let us be inspired and encouraged to further our efforts, both on an individual level and as a unified church community.

I want to conclude this sermon by reading 1 Timothy 5:8. It says: "But if anyone does not provide for his own and especially

for those of his household, he has denied the faith and is worse than an unbeliever.” I interpret “provide for his own” as encompassing the responsibility to care for and accept the elderly within one’s own household. It is imperative that our piety is not merely expressed in words but is tangibly manifested in our actions. Neglecting the care of the elderly equates to a denial of our faith. As we have explored, God displays a distinct concern for the elderly, widows, and widowers. He ensures their well-being, listens to their pleas, ensures justice for them, and employs them in various ways for His divine purpose. This divine perspective should be mirrored in our own lives. May we all be blessed by God’s grace as we endeavor to follow this path.

14

MAKING THE RIGHT DECISION: A SNEAK PEEK INTO THE LIVES OF NAOMI, ORPAH AND RUTH (RUTH 1:8-18)

Sam T. Rajkumar*

Ruth stands out as the sole book in the Bible solely dedicated to recounting the history of a woman. This book shows God's long-suffering with Israel which is demonstrated in Exo. 34:6-7. In the Hebrew Bible, Ruth is put with Psalms, Proverbs, Esther, Ruth, and Song of Solomon. The events recorded cover a period of 10-12 years. The author however is unknown and Biblical characters like Hezekiah, Ezra, or Samuel have been suggested. Books like Ruth, Esther and Judith (Apocrypha) are unique in the OT text as they speak in a primarily feminine voice and leads to the possibility of female authorship. Although the exact authorship of the Book of Ruth cannot be definitively determined, it is evident that the narrative encompasses a distinct feminine perspective. The book addresses issues specific to women, which would have been prevalent in that particular cultural context. Judging by the form of the book, it is quite plausible that Ruth existed in an oral form and in its progression from oral to written with possible editing done, female intervention was present.

* Rev. Sam T. Rajkumar is an accomplished minister with a strong background in children's ministry. He is currently pursuing a Master's degree in Biblical Studies (Old Testament) at The United Theological College, Bengaluru. Sam has penned two books: "Resounding Faith" and "Anime Parables."

The events depicted in the Book of Ruth occur within the timeframe of the period of Judges, which historians generally estimate to span from approximately 1367 to 931 BCE. The data within the Book of Ruth, especially concerning David's reign, elevates the book of Ruth's importance. In the vast majority of Hebrew manuscripts, Ruth is one of the five festival scrolls of Jewish tradition. The opening verse of the Book of Ruth claims it was during the times when the judges ruled Israel and it is this author's opinion that it was. Ruth, despite its setting in the period of Judges, is believed to have been written at a later date. The Book of Ruth structures its scenes in an artistic way, building its way to the climax of a new redeemer with genealogy in the last chapter which we see is later used by Matthew to introduce Jesus in the New Testament. While the Book of Ruth is primarily a historical narrative, there are two sections that are defined as poetry. Two notable speeches in the Book of Ruth include Ruth's first speech to Naomi found in 1:16-17 and Naomi's address to the women of Bethlehem documented in 1:20-21.

Naomi the backslider

The main character's name Naomi actually means good and pleasant. However, this person liked to be called by her another name Mara which meant bitter. It is interesting to note that the Bible never calls her Mara, nor does it show any of her friends doing so. Naomi, who was married to Elimelech, had two sons named Mahlon and Chileon. Alongside her, Naomi had two Moabite daughters-in-law, Ruth and Orpah. Naomi was most likely born in the land of Judah, but migrated with Elimelech to escape the famine in Israel. After her husband died and the famine ended, she returned with Ruth to Bethlehem. The mother-in-law Naomi we see in the Bible was very kind and had truly exceptional daughters-in-law unlike the drama which we commonly see in Television serials. Naomi displayed a range of emotions throughout the narrative, fluctuating between

moments of strength and vulnerability. She was observed weeping alongside her daughters-in-law, expressing gratitude and optimism on certain occasions, while also exhibiting periods of ingratitude and bitterness.

The bad side

Naomi's vulnerability lay in the way she raised her sons, as they married foreign women, contradicting God's command to Israel as mentioned in Ezra 10:10. Additionally, she expressed complaints, bitterness, and ingratitude towards God, claiming that she had returned empty-handed, despite still having Ruth, her own life, her health, and seemingly caring individuals in her hometown. We see Naomi's backsliding nature as she encouraged her daughters-in-law to return to their gods. Can you imagine a child of God encouraging anyone, especially family members, to go back and worship idols and false gods? Naomi did not want her daughters-in-law to go to Bethlehem with her because she was trying to cover up her sin before her town's people. It is possible that Naomi's reluctance to take her daughters-in-law with her stemmed from a concern that their presence would serve as a visible reminder that her sons had married outside their covenant nation. By returning alone, Naomi may have hoped to avoid drawing attention to the fact that her family had violated the Law of Moses. Are we like Naomi who backslides from our commitment to God?

The good side

Naomi was very loyal to her husband in following him from her native land to a foreign place and faithful in returning back to the promised land after her husband's death. She was even kind to her daughters-in-law! Mothers-in-law are usually considered as monsters at home.

Naomi demonstrated kindness and selflessness towards her daughters-in-law by encouraging them to stay in their homeland, despite her own desire for their companionship on the journey. Although she faced moments of vulnerability, she earnestly sought to make wise decisions when given the opportunity. Despite her occasional weaknesses, Naomi ultimately maintained her belief in and trust in the Lord. In the Christian life, doubts and even bitterness can arise, but it is crucial to navigate through those challenges and rekindle trust in and love for the Lord. Are we willing to come out of our Backsliding nature and trust God like Naomi?

Orpah the mere professor

Biblical names carry significant meanings, and the name Orpah has multiple interpretations. One interpretation links it to the Hebrew word “Oreph,” which means “neck.” This association could suggest that Orpah was considered stiff-necked since she turned away from her mother-in-law after her husband’s death and returned to her own people. Other translation’s view Orpah’s name as referencing a fawn or gazelle, symbolizing young and easily startled animals capable of swift escape. Orpah became the wife of Naomi’s son, Kilion. Some theories propose that Orpah and Ruth were sisters prior to their marriages, potentially being daughters of the king of Moab. Regardless, they adhered to different traditions and held distinct beliefs. It can be argued that Naomi’s family deviated from their homeland’s customs and adopted foreign practices. Upon learning of the end of the famine in Bethlehem, Naomi chose to return home. She encouraged both Orpah and Ruth to go back to their people, but they initially resisted. While Ruth strongly refused to leave Naomi, Orpah eventually yielded to her mother-in-law’s plea. It is important to note the moment before Orpah’s departure – she wept aloud. Leaving Naomi was not a simple decision for her; it was a difficult and painful choice.

The bad side

Orpah, having grown up in a background that worshipped false idols, lacked a deep-rooted faith in God to sustain her through potential hardships. Unlike Ruth, who wholeheartedly committed to following the God of Naomi, Orpah did not possess such faith and made no promises. Although she deeply loved her mother-in-law, it was not enough for her to risk the uncertainties of her future. Orpah's desires were conflicted, as she had Bethlehem in her sight but Moab still held her heart. Both daughters-in-law initially decided to accompany Naomi back to Bethlehem, but while Ruth's commitment remained faithful and enduring, Orpah's commitment wavered. Orpah serves as a portrayal of a superficial believer who merely professes faith but lacks genuine dedication, thus fading into the background of the story. She shed tears, similar to Ruth, and displayed emotions, even kissing Naomi, but ultimately returned to Moab. Her faith amounted to nothing more than outward appearances. Are we like Orpah who had a worldly surface commitment to God?

The good side

While it is common to criticize Orpah for her perceived lack of faithfulness, a closer examination of the entire story in context allows for a better understanding of her actions. It is important to celebrate Ruth's faithfulness while also developing empathy for Orpah and the difficult decisions she faced. Orpah genuinely listened to Naomi's plea. In biblical times, women depended on men for their survival, as men provided shelter and sustenance. If Orpah continued with Naomi, she knew that her future would be uncertain. Unlike us, Orpah did not have the advantage of knowing Ruth's story's happy ending. Her decision was far from easy. Orpah's tears upon parting with her mother and sister-in-law were not merely expressions of sadness but reflections of her deep disturbance. Taking a closer look at her circumstances

helps us recognize that she, too, was a human being trying to make what she believed were the best decisions for her life. Orpah's decision sheds light on the challenges faced by single and widowed women in the past. Understanding all of this enhances the remarkable nature of Ruth's story. Are we willing to develop sympathy for people like Orpah?

Ruth the real possessor

The Hebrew name "Ruth" carries the meaning of "friendship" and conveys the concepts of consistency, steadfastness, and commitment. Ruth, hailing from Moab, a land of Gentiles, was generally despised by many Jews due to their foreign gods and perceived uncleanness. In her time, when a foreigner married a believer, it often resulted in the believer being led astray into idolatry. However, Ruth stood out from the norm as she assimilated into Jewish culture and wholeheartedly embraced the true God as her own. She likely fulfilled the role of a housewife, as was customary during that era, and the death of her husband forced her to work in the fields to earn a living. Ruth is portrayed as one of the most devout women in the Bible and holds significant prominence in the genealogies of both David and Jesus. While no specific exceptional abilities of Ruth are mentioned, her extraordinary commitment stands out as she was among the very few Gentiles throughout the Old Testament who willingly relinquished their own lifestyle, people, country, and idols in order to follow God.

The bad side

One intriguing aspect of the Book of Ruth is that it does not explicitly mention any weaknesses in Ruth's life, although it is plausible that she may have had some challenges or shortcomings. A historical anecdote illustrates the depth of devotion and sacrifice: Cyrus, the founder of the Persian Empire, once captured a prince and his family. When asked what he

would give in exchange for their release, the prince offered half of his wealth for himself, everything he possessed for his children, and ultimately offered himself for his wife's freedom. Touched by his unwavering commitment, Cyrus freed them all. On their journey back home, the prince remarked on Cyrus' handsome appearance, to which his wife, brimming with profound love, responded, "I did not notice. I could only keep my eyes on you, the one who was willing to give himself for me." Ruth, similarly sacrificial and loyal to her family and God, left a lasting legacy, culminating in the Bible dedicating an entire book to her. Are we willing to be sacrificial and loyal to God and Family like Ruth did?

The good side

Ruth was highly regarded for her godly character, which holds more value than fame or wealth. A profound expression of loyalty can be found in Ruth 1:16-17, making it one of the most heartfelt declarations in the Old Testament. The Bible portrays Ruth's relationship with Naomi as unbreakable. Despite having the option to leave Naomi and pursue her own aspirations at any given moment, Ruth remained steadfast. She cared for and provided for Naomi to such an extent that their bond became widely known throughout the town. The townspeople even acknowledged that Ruth was more valuable to Naomi than seven sons! God always cares for believers and honours their decision to follow Him and prioritize Him in their lives. Ruth made a significant sacrifice to uphold what was right, and God blessed her for it. While such blessings may not always manifest on this earth, Ruth and Naomi experienced them. God never forgets His children or forsakes them. Ruth's actions teach us profound lessons about God's faithfulness. She persevered through dire circumstances and demonstrated unwavering love towards Naomi. Her faithfulness was met with divine intervention when God orchestrated her meeting with Boaz in the field. They

married, and Ruth became an integral part of the lineage of king David and Jesus Christ. Are we willing to make great decision of following God like Ruth did no matter what the situation is?

Naomi tried to cover-up, Orpah gave-up, but Ruth stood up!

Which character do we resemble in our own lives? If we find ourselves drifting away from God, are we willing to make the right decision and turn back to God, just as Naomi did? If our commitment to God is primarily external and superficial, like Orpah, are we willing to undergo an internal transformation and help our friends, like Orpah, make the right decisions in their lives? While Orpah chose to leave, Ruth remained steadfast and wholeheartedly declared her choice to follow Naomi and the true God. Are we willing to make the same choice that Ruth made? Will we choose to place our faith in God today?

Our sins may separate us from God, but through the lineage of Ruth, Jesus has provided a way for us to be reconciled with Him and become part of His family. Will we confess our sins and fully commit ourselves to our loving God, Jesus Christ, who sacrificed Himself for us, granting us the opportunity to become members of His family today?

In our modern lives, we can see parallels to the characters in the book of Ruth. Like Naomi, we may sometimes find ourselves trying to hide our struggles and difficulties, pretending that everything is fine. However, true transformation begins when we acknowledge our need for God and make the choice to turn back to God. Many of us may also relate to Orpah, who initially showed an outward commitment to God but lacked a genuine internal transformation. This calls us to examine our own faith and ensure that it goes beyond mere appearances, seeking a deep and authentic relationship with God. On the other hand, Ruth's unwavering loyalty and dedication serve as an inspiration. Her resolute decision to follow God and support Naomi encourages

us to make similar choices in our own lives. We are challenged to embrace faithfulness and demonstrate unwavering commitment to God and those around us, even in challenging circumstances.

The message from Ruth 1:8-18 calls us to reflect on our own faith journey. It urges us to make intentional decisions to follow God, confess our sins, and commit ourselves wholeheartedly to His loving embrace. Through Jesus Christ, we can experience the transformative power of God's grace and become part of His eternal family.

15

MANONETRA — THE POWER OF INTUITION

A REFLECTION ON MARK 10:46-52

Albert Simon Emmaniel*

Manonetra is the term used in Sanskrit which means ‘intuition.’ It has the meaning of inner eye or mind’s eye. Intuition is a form of knowledge that is not based on conscious reasoning or analytic thought, but rather on unconscious processes such as instinct, gut-feeling, and awareness. Some people are naturally more intuitive than others, but intuition can also be developed through practices involving mindfulness, self-awareness, and reflection. It relies on accessing a deeper level of awareness or consciousness beyond the rational mind.

This concept of *Manonetra* is not new to us though the word is absent in the Bible. The idea is present from Old Testament times which we can see in 2 Kings 6:17 where Elisha prays to God: “O Lord, please open his eyes that he may see.” The Lord opened the eyes of the servant. Here, the onus is not on seeing the physical world, rather the seeing through his *Manonetra*.

We are all familiar with the scriptural passage Mark 10:46-52. This passage is the story of a blind man where Jesus is hailed as “Son of David.” Only Mark gave the name of the person who was healed and this is the only place where he did so. I

* Albert Simon Emmaniel is from CSI Rayalaseema Diocese who pursues his final year BD in The United Theological College, Bengaluru. This sermon was written for senior worship service on July 10, 2023.

wondered why only Bartimaeus' name was written and began thinking about the person and his efforts to obtain healing.

When the name is given in the text, it has a deeper meaning to understand. The vast majority of people whom Jesus healed are anonymous; in fact, most of them are unnamed but Bartimaeus' name was preserved and it must therefore be significant. The name means 'son of Timai.' The meaning of Timai is 'honoured.' But, Bartimaeus was represented in the passage as marginalised, poor and oppressed. With his physical disability and his consequent need to beg for survival, Bartimaeus was doubly oppressed. Now, we need to know how *Manonetra* (the power of intuition) changed an oppressed individual into becoming an honoured person in the society.

Intuition as a gift of God

We, humans, have five primary senses, eye (visual), ear (auditory), nose (olfactory), mouth (gustatory), and skin (cutaneous) which help us to sense the things around us. These senses are referred to as "gateways to knowledge." Human life would be very challenging without our ability to sense and perceive. Without the ability to sense and perceive, we could not move. Each of our senses uses its own detection system to get information from our surroundings. The information is sent to the brain where it is processed and combined to create a complete sensory picture of our environment. In effect, mind connects sense organs and objects with the intellect. Intellect processes the incoming knowledge and the processed knowledge is stored in soul.

In this text, we see a man who was absolutely blind. There is a proverb in *Neeti Satakam*, i.e., "Sarvendriyanam Nayanam Pradhanam" which means eye is important among all senses. The bible also says in Matthew 6:22: "The eye is the lamp of the body. So, if your eye is healthy, your whole body will be full of light; but if your eye is unhealthy, your whole body will be full

of darkness.” Bartimaeus could see nothing with the physical eyes with which he had been born. This man was completely dependent upon those who would toss him a few coins so he could buy enough food to survive another day. He had no service he could perform. He was stuck.

This incident involving the healing of Bartimaeus took place during the final stage of Jesus’ journey to Jerusalem. This man was blind physically, but he had his ears opened and the wheels of his mind revolved furiously in his life of darkness. He had a super vision with which he could see through the mind’s eye (*Manonetrām*). He took seriously the hearsay of many conversations and put together all the information collected/perceived. Bartimaeus had the ability to think and reason.

Bartimaeus knew something about this one man, who was the greatest of all the kings of Judah. His mind pieced together bits of information he knew and had heard. Who knows how a differently-abled Bartimaeus, who was begging acquired such profound information about Jesus! He had perceived so much about Jesus of Nazareth. Indeed, it appeared that everyone was talking about him. The ladies passing by on their way to the market were praising Jesus’ virtues. The men gathered on the street to transact business were discussing Jesus’ miracles and wondering who he was. With his acute hearing, Bartimaeus picked up all the information. He had stored all this information in his mind and through his awareness and intuition he set his goal and hopes on Jesus.

Bartimaeus intuitively identified and recognized Jesus as the Son of David. A close reading of the passage suggests that Bartimaeus knew more than we can imagine about his knowledge. In Bartimaeus’ case, he likely used his “mind’s eye” (*manonetra*) to envision Jesus coming his way and sensed his presence. Bartimaeus had to rely on his other senses and his intuition in order to navigate the world around him. He may not have been

able to physically see Jesus but he heard about Jesus, he was able to recognize him through a deeper and spiritual sense.

Faith in terms of intuition

Bartimaeus' intuition started a new faith in his life. He did not bother about his situation but he was waiting for the opportunity. Once he heard that Jesus was passing through that way, his intuition did not allow him to sit quietly. He identified his need and attempted to grab Jesus' attention. But no one cared about his attempt because he was marginalized and side-lined; he was begging on the roadside. He was viewed as being stupid and ignorant, and may be a nuisance to the society. The people did not see his struggle. In fact, they did not care what he was trying to do. Through his intuition, Bartimaeus knew that Jesus could heal him and alleviate his oppression.

Just imagine the place when Jesus was passing through, the people of Jericho were lining up on the roadside. Many people were there in anticipation to see this one named Jesus who was a miracle worker. And among them was this blind beggar, probably not well-bathed or fresh-looking. I can imagine how they treated this man on the suppressed class of society. I do not think they were saying 'please.' They were saying 'be quiet'; in v. 48 we see the word 'rebuked'; this word is used in the sense of scolding; literally they said 'Stop shouting! Shut up! Be quiet!'

Bartimaeus knew this was his opportunity and he persisted in calling out for Jesus' mercy even when others told him to be quiet. He reminds us of the importance and power of persistence. Bartimaeus did not give up. Bartimaeus started shouting "Jesus, Son of David, have mercy on me" instead of letting the people suppress him. He cried out more loudly. He knew that Jesus was his only hope, and he was determined to reach him no matter what obstacles he faced. He captured the attention of Jesus through his effort. The term "Son of David" used by Bartimaeus

was like a precursor to the Jews who used the same term to address Jesus when he entered Jerusalem in his glory in chapter 11. Bartimaeus' intuition allowed him to see beyond his physical limitations and trust in the power of God's love and mercy. His persistence adds substance to his bold expression of "faith alone."

Collective power of intuition in liberation from oppression

Bartimaeus' struggle was to achieve his vision. His ultimate vision was to receive his eye sight. Bartimaeus does not choose temporary solutions available to him. At any time of the year the place where he begged was mostly a crowded place. A guaranteed crowd meant a guaranteed income for Bartimaeus. He did not want to go for that guaranteed income. He wanted to listen to the voice of his intuition, that is *Manonetra*. It was his intuition and mind's eye which made him aim at the perfect and ultimate goal with the expectation of liberation from oppression.

When Jesus stopped and said "call him," the people who tried to make him quiet or oppress him suddenly changed their voice; instead of "scolding and shutting him up," they started saying, "Take heart! Be encouraged! Get up! He is calling you." Bartimaeus was honoured here because of his efforts through his intuition.

In v. 50, Bartimaeus threw off his cloak. Throwing off his cloak meant shrugging off his old way of life. He drew away from his comfort zone. He had enough of being defined and identified as a beggar. He did not just toss aside a jacket or sweater . . . this was a moment of life or death. Bartimaeus was confident when he was called by Jesus. He was so desperate for the change.

Next, when Jesus asked him "What do you want me to do for you?" Bartimaeus boldly told Jesus he wanted to see. That was a real and honest answer to the question. His focus, struggle,

and attempt helped Bartimaeus to accomplish his mission for his vision.

Conclusion

Dear friends it is not only in the case of Bartimaeus, but also in the case of one more strong New Testament character who had all the vision, who had all the intricacies of the theology of the then times, yet what he could see was just violence; what he could see was the fundamentalist kind of discipleship; but then when he lost his sight on the way to Damascus and then regained it later (probably only partially), the impact which resulted after he regained his sight, the impact on society, the impact on today's Christianity is much profound than what it was when he could actually see physically with all his theological qualifications. This encounter not only transformed Paul's life but also redirected his purpose and mission, leading him to become one of the most influential figures in the spread of the gospel.

Learning from him, we should become as knowledgeable as we can in order to be aware of more opportunities that we can take advantage of situations through *Manonetra*. No matter what that opportunity might be, people who cannot see you succeeding may try to oppress you but we need to be conscious all around.

Let us be bold enough to follow our instincts, which are gifts from God, believing that the Lord is guiding us in that direction. When our intuition is grounded in God's Word, submitted to the guidance of the Holy Spirit, and in line with God's wisdom, it will guard us against mistakes and assist in keeping us on the right road.

My dear Friends, the darkness that is around you is meant to expose the light that is within you that is, *Manonetra*. May the Almighty help us to see through our *Manonetra*!

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THE UNITED THEOLOGICAL COLLEGE

63, Miller's Road, Benson Town, Bengaluru - 560 046, India.

Phone : 080-2333 2844 / 3438 / 0502, Fax : 080-2333 0015

E-mail : masihisevak@gmail.com | www.utcbangalore.org